

HARMONISED PRACTICES, REGULATIONS AND STANDARDS
IN WASTE MANAGEMENT AND DECOMMISSIONING

Deliverable D6.1

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

K.N. van Zweel, T. Schatz (VTT), T. Braunroth (GRS), P. François, F. Millet (ASNR), S. Konopaskova, H. Vojtechova (SURO)

Technical Research Centre of Finland VTT Ltd
Maarintie 3 (VTT main building, VTT FutureHub)

02150 Espoo, Finland

karl.vanzweel@vtt.fi

Version: 1

Date: 08/04/2025

Dissemination level: Public

HARMONISED PRACTICES, REGULATIONS AND STANDARDS
IN WASTE MANAGEMENT AND DECOMMISSIONING

DELIVERABLE D6.1

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

PROJECT REFERENCES

- **Project acronym:** HARPERS
- **Project title:** HARmonised PracticEs, Regulations and Standards in waste management and decommissioning
- **Grant agreement No.** 101060028

DELIVERABLE REFERENCES

- **Deliverable title:** Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)
- **Deliverable no:** D6.1
- **Version:** 1
- **Type:** Deliverable/report
- **Dissemination level:** Public
- **Due date:** 30th April 2025
- **Lead beneficiary:** VTT
- **WP No:** 6
- **Main author:** Karl Nicolaus VAN ZWEEL
- **Reviewed by:** Tim SCHATZ
- **Accepted by:** Elke JACOBS & Réka SZŐKE
- **Contributing author(s):** Patrice FRANCOIS, François MILLET, Thomas BRAUNROTH, Sona KONOPASKOVA, Hana VOJTECHOVA
- **pg:** 124

ABSTRACT

This report presents the outcomes of Work Package 6 (WP6) of the HARPERS project, which aimed to assess regulatory alignment across the European Union in the areas of radioactive waste management (RWM) and decommissioning. Drawing on findings from other HARPERS work packages — WP3 (cross-border services and facilities), WP4 (circular economy), and WP5 (advanced technologies) — WP6 consolidates insights from expert consultations, stakeholder input, and regulatory analyses to identify recurring challenges and propose areas for improvement.

The analysis shows that while formal regulatory frameworks are generally in place, practical obstacles may arise from differences in national interpretation, planning approaches, and technical implementation. These obstacles are evident in areas such as the classification of problematic and hazardous waste, clearance and reuse of decommissioned materials, and the integration of emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, robotics, and digital twins. These incongruities can hinder innovation, cross-border cooperation, and the adoption of circular economy principles.

By applying a structured classification methodology, WP6 distinguishes between issues that are regulatory in origin and those that stem from strategic, technical, or perceived barriers. The findings support the need for greater clarity in definitions, more consistent regulatory guidance, and enhanced coordination among Member States.

To address these challenges, the report proposes six cross-cutting priority actions: (1) harmonising definitions and classification standards; (2) updating EU-level guidance and tools; (3) developing more specific regulatory frameworks for advanced technologies; (4) improving strategic alignment and planning coordination; (5) strengthening regulatory capacity and stakeholder engagement; and (6) promoting mutual recognition of national certifications, clearance procedures, and regulatory decisions, along with enhanced cross-border cooperation in waste transport, treatment, and disposal.

Targeted action in these areas can improve the effectiveness and consistency of regulatory practices across the EU, while supporting safe, efficient, and sustainable decommissioning and waste management strategies.

Administrative coordinator contact:

Elke Jacops
SCK CEN Belgian Nuclear Research
Centre
Boeretang 200, 2400 Mol, Belgium
Email: elke.jacops@sckcen.be
Tel 0032 485 274196

Technical coordinator contact:

Réka Szóke
IFE Institute for Energy Technology
Os Alle 5, NO-1777 Halden, Norway
Email: reka.szoke@ife.no
Tel 0047 452 85963

The use of the name of any authors or organization in advertising or publication in part of this report is only permissible with written authorisation from IFE and SCK CEN.

Acknowledgement

This project has received funding from the Euratom research and training programme 2021-27 under GA No 101060028.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

Contents

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	- 7 -
1. REGULATORY FRAMEWORK AND CRITERIA REPORT (WP6)	- 9 -
1.1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	- 9 -
2 INTRODUCTION	- 12 -
2.1 BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT.....	- 12 -
2.2 STRUCTURE OF THE REPORT	- 12 -
3 THE EVOLUTION OF NUCLEAR REGULATION IN THE EU	- 15 -
3.1 THE EURATOM TREATY AS THE FOUNDATIONAL FRAMEWORK	- 15 -
3.2 EU SECONDARY LEGISLATION AND REGULATORY INSTRUMENTS	- 15 -
3.3 NATIONAL TRANSPOSITION: HOW MS IMPLEMENT EU DIRECTIVES	- 16 -
3.4 THE ROLE OF INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS	- 20 -
3.4.1 <i>European Nuclear Safety Regulators Group (ENSREG)</i>	- 21 -
3.4.2 <i>International Conventions and Treaties</i>	- 21 -
3.4.3 <i>International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA)</i>	- 22 -
3.4.4 <i>OECD/Nuclear Energy Agency (NEA)</i>	- 23 -
3.4.5 <i>Western European Nuclear Regulators Association (WENRA)</i>	- 23 -
3.5 COMPLEMENTARITY AND OVERLAP AMONG INTERNATIONAL EFFORTS.....	- 24 -
3.6 EFFECTIVENESS, CHALLENGES, AND GAPS IN HARMONIZATION	- 25 -
3.7 HARPERS AREAS OF INTEREST	- 28 -
3.7.1 <i>Cross border services / facilities</i>	- 28 -
3.7.2 <i>Circular Economy in Decommissioning (Material Reuse)</i>	- 32 -
3.7.3 <i>Advanced Technologies: Robotics, BIM, and Digital Twins</i>	- 34 -

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

4	METHODOLOGY	- 38 -
4.1	INTRODUCTION	- 38 -
4.2	WP6-SPECIFIC ANALYSIS METHODOLOGY.....	- 38 -
4.2.1	<i>Classification Framework for Problem Statements</i>	- 39 -
4.2.2	<i>Refined Classes for Problem Statements</i>	- 39 -
4.2.3	<i>Analytical Tools and Techniques Used</i>	- 41 -
4.2.4	<i>Framework for Classification</i>	- 42 -
5	RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	- 44 -
5.1	INTRODUCTION	- 44 -
5.2	REGULATORY IMPACT ON THE ALIGNMENT OF WASTES WITH TREATMENT TECHNOLOGIES.....	- 44 -
5.2.1	<i>Analysis of issues:</i>	- 46 -
5.2.2	<i>Conclusion</i>	- 47 -
5.3	WP4 REGULATORY FRAMEWORK AND CRITERIA REPORT.....	- 48 -
5.3.1	<i>Analysis of issues:</i>	- 50 -
5.3.2	<i>Conclusion</i>	- 51 -
5.4	WP5 REGULATORY FRAMEWORK.....	- 52 -
5.4.1	<i>Analysis of issues:</i>	- 54 -
5.4.2	<i>Conclusion</i>	- 56 -
6	CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	- 58 -
6.1	INTRODUCTION	- 58 -
6.2	WP3 – CROSS BORDER SERVICES / FACILITIES	- 58 -
6.3	WP4 – CIRCULAR ECONOMY.....	- 61 -

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

6.4	WP5 – ADVANCED TECHNOLOGIES.....	- 63 -
6.5	CONCLUSION.....	- 65 -
7	REFERENCES.....	- 67 -

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full Form
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ARTEMIS	Assessment and Review under The Integrated Review Service for Radioactive Waste and Spent Fuel Management, Decommissioning and Remediation
ASN	Autorité de Sûreté Nucléaire (France)
ASNR	Autorité de Sûreté Nucléaire et de Radioprotection
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BSS	Basic Safety Standards
CDLM	Committee on Decommissioning of Nuclear Installations and Legacy Management
DT	Digital Twin
EC	European Commission
ENSREG	European Nuclear Safety Regulators Group
ERDO	European Repository Development Organisation
EU	European Union
EURATOM	European Atomic Energy Community
FOAK	First Of A Kind
GSR	General Safety Requirements (IAEA safety standards)
HLW	High-Level Waste
IAEA	International Atomic Energy Agency
ICRP	International Commission on Radiological Protection
IRRS	Integrated Regulatory Review Service
IRSN	Institut de Radioprotection et de Sûreté Nucléaire (France)
IT	Information Technology
JRC	Joint Research Centre (of the European Commission)
LILW	low- and intermediate-level radioactive wastes
MCA	Multi-Criteria Analysis
MS	Member State(s)
NDA	Nuclear Decommissioning Authority (UK)
NEA	Nuclear Energy Agency
NPP	Nuclear Power Plant
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
ONR	Office for Nuclear Regulation (UK)
RAW	Radioactive Waste
RWM	Radioactive Waste Management
RWMC	Radioactive Waste Management Committee
SMR	Small Modular Reactor
SOGIN	Società Gestione Impianti Nucleari (Italy)
SRL	Safety Reference Level
SURO	National Radiation Protection Institute (Czech Republic)
TECDOC	Technical Document (IAEA)
UK	United Kingdom
VLLW	Very Low-Level Waste

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

VTT	Technical Research Centre of Finland
WAC	Waste Acceptance Criteria
WENRA	Western European Nuclear Regulators Association
WGWD	Working Group on Waste Disposal
WP	Work Package

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

1. Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

1.1 Executive Summary

This report presents an integrated analysis of purported regulatory challenges affecting nuclear decommissioning and waste management and the implementation of advanced technologies and circular economy principles within the European Union (EU). Drawing on findings from the EURATOM HARPERS project — specifically Milestones MS20 (WP3), MS21 (WP4), and MS22 (WP5) — the report consolidates insights from expert consultations, stakeholder questionnaires, and technical reviews across multiple Member States (MS). The aim is to identify commonly encountered regulatory, strategic, and technical barriers — such as inconsistent waste classifications, unclear clearance procedures, or lack of guidance on emerging technologies — and to support the development of proportionate, innovation-ready, and sustainability-oriented regulatory frameworks.

Each of the upstream HARPERS work packages (WP3-5) undertook a dedicated task to identify regulatory challenges within their broader scopes of work. The resulting regulatory framework and criteria reports provided targeted inputs for WP6, enabling a consolidated assessment of potential regulatory issues across these thematic areas.

HARPERS WP3, in part, examined challenges related to the classification and cross-border management of problematic and hazardous radioactive waste (RAW). The WP6 analysis found that while a few issues are regulatory in nature — particularly those around the definition of problematic waste and differing legal interpretations of hazardous RAW—most others stem from implementation practices, administrative complexity, or strategic prioritisation at the national level. Notably, existing legislation already permits cross-border cooperation in most cases, and successful examples (e.g., services provided by Orano and Cyclife) demonstrate that practical pathways can be found under current frameworks.

HARPERS WP4 included an assessment on how regulatory frameworks influence the integration of circular economy practices into nuclear decommissioning and waste

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

management, particularly in relation to material clearance and reuse. The analysis highlighted that many challenges relate to differences in national interpretation, procedural burdens, and the absence of up-to-date technical support. While some issues were classified as regulatory—such as inconsistent transposition of EU directives or a lack of correspondence between nuclear and conventional waste governance—others were strategic or technical in nature, reflecting planning gaps and outdated guidance. There is a need for clearer alignment, harmonised tools, and broader decision-making approaches that balance radiological safety with sustainability goals.

HARPERS WP5, looked into potential regulatory challenges associated with the adoption of advanced technologies in decommissioning and waste management, including digital twins, artificial intelligence (AI), robotics, and building information modelling (BIM). Of the nineteen issues identified by WP5, only four could be classified as regulatory in nature. These relate to the absence of clear regulatory frameworks for emerging technologies, the slow pace of regulatory adaptation, and ambiguities in cybersecurity classification. Other issues involved technical standards, regulatory awareness, and international coordination. Overall, the findings emphasise the importance of early engagement, capacity-building, and adaptive regulatory approaches to ensure both safety and innovation.

Across all three work packages, a common theme emerged: although formal regulations are generally in place, there are clear opportunities to improve regulatory alignment, practical implementation, and strategic coordination. Most of the barriers identified do not stem from legislative gaps, but from variations in interpretation, outdated supporting tools, and the need for more structured, inclusive, and sustained engagement among regulators, operators, and technology developers.

Key recommendations include:

- Supporting greater consistency in the interpretation and application of EU regulatory frameworks.
- Clarifying definitions and classifications — particularly for problematic waste and advanced digital tools.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

- Updating technical guidance and developing standardised tools to support implementation.
- Encouraging early and structured dialogue between stakeholders to improve regulatory understanding.
- Promoting broader decision-making frameworks that integrate radiological safety with environmental, economic, and social considerations.

In conclusion, the report underlines the importance of implementing targeted, evidence-based actions to address evident regulatory challenges — whether through improved guidance, harmonised approaches, or capacity-building. Ensuring that regulatory systems remain clear, coherent, and responsive will be key to achieving both safe decommissioning and waste management outcomes and broader sustainability objectives across the European nuclear sector.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

2 Introduction

2.1 Background and Context

The HARPERS project (HARmonised PracticEs, Regulations, and Standards in radioactive waste management and decommissioning) is part of the Euratom Research and Training Programme. It aims to support improved alignment in the regulatory environment surrounding radioactive waste management and decommissioning activities across EU Member States. By focusing on harmonisation, the project seeks to facilitate cross-border cooperation, advance circular economy principles, and enable the adoption of innovative technologies in the nuclear back end.

The project spans 36 months and brings together a wide range of stakeholders, including regulators, technical support organisations (TSOs), waste management organisations (WMOs), industry representatives, and research institutions. Through collaboration and coordination, HARPERS promotes the exchange of knowledge and best practices to strengthen safety, efficiency, and innovation in the sector.

Work Package 6 (WP6) plays a specific role in evaluating whether the challenges identified in upstream work packages — WP3 (cross-border services), WP4 (circular economy), and WP5 (advanced technologies) — can be understood as regulatory issues in the context of EU-level harmonisation. WP6 also aims to identify opportunities for greater regulatory coherence across Member States. In doing so, it supports the development of proportionate and innovation-ready frameworks that align with both technical realities and policy objectives.

The work of WP6 is further informed through synergies with related projects, including EURAD, PREDIS, and SHARE, contributing to a broader European effort to build regulatory clarity and capacity in nuclear decommissioning and waste management.

2.2 Structure of the Report

This report presents the work of Work Package 6 (WP6), which aimed to assess whether the challenges identified in three upstream work packages — cross-border

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

services and facilities (WP3), circular economy practices (WP4), and advanced technologies (WP5) — can be understood as regulatory in nature, and to evaluate how these challenges relate to differences in interpretation, application, and implementation of EU directives and international standards across Member States. The goal is to provide a clearer understanding of how regulatory approaches vary between countries, and how this variation may influence the adoption of safe, effective, and sustainable practices in nuclear decommissioning and waste management.

To support this assessment, the report is structured in four main parts:

- Section 1 and 2 introduce the objectives and context of the HARPERS project, clarify the specific role of WP6 within the project, and outline how WP6 builds on findings from WP3, WP4, and WP5. This section also defines key terms used in the report, including the meaning of “regulatory alignment” as consistency in interpretation and application across Member States, rather than any formal harmonization of laws.
- Section 3 provides an overview of the development of nuclear regulatory frameworks in the EU, describing the interplay of EU directives, international standards (e.g., IAEA), and national transposition into domestic law. This section explains why differences in regulatory approaches exist between countries, reflecting variations in legal systems, policy priorities, and historical contexts — even while all Member States comply with overarching EU and IAEA requirements. By establishing this context, Section 3 offers a rationale for why differences in interpretation and implementation exist across Member States.
- Section 4 describes the methodology used in WP6 to assess the potential regulatory challenges identified in WP3, WP4, and WP5. It explains how issues were classified as regulatory, technical, strategic, or perceived, and how expert input and international benchmarks were used to validate these classifications.
- Section 5 presents the results of the WP6 analysis, applying the classification framework to the issues collected from the upstream work packages. This section explores whether identified challenges reflect differences in regulatory interpretation, procedural implementation, or broader strategic and technical factors.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

- Section 6 offers conclusions and recommendations, drawing on the findings to propose potential ways to improve clarity, consistency, and coordination across Member States, while respecting national legal frameworks and regulatory responsibilities.

By organizing the report in this way, the aim is to provide both the background necessary to understand the diversity of regulatory approaches in the EU, and a structured assessment of how these differences relate to the challenges identified in WP3, WP4, and WP5.

3 The Evolution of Nuclear Regulation in the EU

3.1 The EURATOM Treaty as the Foundational Framework

The Treaty establishing the European Atomic Energy Community (EURATOM) is one of the core treaties of the European Union (Treaty, 1957). It provides the fundamental legal basis for EU-level action in the nuclear field, covering health and safety, supply of nuclear materials, research, and more. No EU law can contradict its overarching provisions, making EURATOM the root source of legislative authority for nuclear matters in the EU. Under this treaty, EU institutions are empowered to adopt legally binding measures — for instance, directives in the areas of nuclear safety, radiation protection, and waste management [1].

3.2 EU Secondary Legislation and Regulatory Instruments

Building on the EURATOM Treaty (and broader EU mechanisms), the EU institutions — namely the European Commission, the Council, and the Parliament — adopt secondary legislation [2]. These legal instruments have direct or indirect effects on Member States, with three primary forms relevant to nuclear regulation:

- **Regulations** are binding immediately and directly applicable in all Member States; they do not require transposition into national law. While direct nuclear regulations are less common, any EU regulation adopted under EURATOM must be followed “as is” by each MS.
- **Directives** are binding with respect to the outcomes they prescribe, but individual MS retain the freedom to determine the specific form and methods of implementation. Several notable directives govern the nuclear field, including:
 - *Basic Safety Standards (BSS) Directive* (2013/59/Euratom): Defines key requirements for radiation protection, such as clearance levels and dose limits [3].
 - *Nuclear Safety Directive* (2009/71/Euratom, amended by 2014/87/Euratom): Establishes a framework for the nuclear safety of installations [4].

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

- *Spent Fuel and Radioactive Waste Directive (2011/70/Euratom)*: Sets requirements for the responsible management of spent fuel and radioactive waste [5].

MS must transpose these directives into their national legal and regulatory frameworks by the specified deadlines, ensuring that minimum standards are met — or exceeded — domestically.

- **Decisions** address specific issues or parties and are binding in their entirety upon those to whom they are addressed. While less frequent in the nuclear domain compared to directives, decisions may arise in Commission rulings concerning particular nuclear installations or cross-border waste shipments.

3.3 National Transposition: How MS Implement EU Directives

European countries take different approaches to implementing Euratom directives, shaped by their legal systems, political priorities, and technical capabilities. To structure this variation, we group MS into three main transposition models: Integrative, Adaptive, and Minimalist. This categorization reflects the extent and manner in which countries incorporate Euratom directives into national law. While the terminology used here is specific to this analysis, the distinctions are grounded in established patterns observed across the EU [6], particularly in the degree of legal adaptation, regulatory engagement, and alignment with international safety standards, as noted in EC assessments and comparative studies.

Integrative Model:

Countries with strong nuclear industries and independent regulators — such as France, Finland, Germany, Sweden, and Belgium — use EU directives as a chance to enhance their national laws. However, they often go beyond EU requirements to follow international safety standards. Their motivation comes from a strong safety culture, public expectations, and expert influence.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

Adaptive Model:

States like the UK (before Brexit), the Netherlands, the Czech Republic, Slovakia, and Slovenia meet EU requirements but adjust them to fit national needs. They may combine new and existing rules to avoid unnecessary regulation, maintaining high safety standards. This approach is guided by practical concerns, industry input, and moderate political support, aiming to comply without adding excessive burden.

Minimalist Model:

Countries with limited nuclear activity or administrative capacity — such as Greece, Portugal, Luxembourg, and initially Romania — only make the minimum legal changes needed to meet EU obligations. They often rely on the EU's wording and guidance, due to limited national expertise or interest. These countries usually enforce the basic requirements once transposed, sometimes with external assistance.

Each model is influenced by legal tradition and the level of national commitment to nuclear safety. Civil-law countries tend to adopt detailed legal measures, while others favour more flexible, results-based regulations. Where nuclear issues are a priority, governments adopt stricter rules to ensure safety and public confidence. Where they are not, compliance tends to be minimal unless required by external pressure.

Table 1: **Current approaches to EU directive transposition:** Overview of MS transposition strategies, legal instruments, institutional roles, and levels of regulatory centralization and stringency.MS.

Transposition Model	MS (examples)	Legal Instruments & Institutions	Centralization	Stringency vs EU Standards
Integrative (comprehensive, proactive)	France, Finland, Germany, Sweden, Belgium, Czechia	New or overhauled Acts and detailed decrees integrating directives (e.g. French Public Health Code update; German Strahlenschutzgesetz). Strong independent regulators (ASN, STUK, etc.) involved in drafting and enforcement.	Highly centralized (national authorities lead; federal states coordinate under national law where applicable).	Often exceed minimum EU requirements (“gold-plating”) for added safety. Incorporate IAEA/WENRA best practices and stricter limits.
Adaptive (moderate, context-tailored)	UK (pre-2020), the Netherlands, Slovenia, Slovakia, Hungary, Italy	Amendments to existing laws or secondary legislation (regulations, ministerial decrees) aligning directives with national frameworks. Regulators and sectoral ministries collaborate (e.g. HSE/ONR in UK; Slovenian SNSA updates Act).	Centralized, with some delegation (e.g. UK devolved administrations issued parallel regs; Italy involves regional agencies for medical uses).	Match EU standards, occasionally earlier implementation or minor extra provisions to fit domestic practices [7]. Avoid major over-implementation but maintain any

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

				higher pre-existing national standards.
Minimalist (literal, compliance-driven)	Greece, Portugal, Luxembourg, Romania, Bulgaria, Malta, Cyprus	Simplified transposition via government regulations or administrative orders. Often uses EU wording directly. Limited involvement of legislature (except where required for a new Act).	Centralized on paper; in practice may lean on external templates. Little regional role (few nuclear activities).	No stricter than EU minimum – focus is on basic compliance. Some initial delays or gaps until prompted by EU infringement procedures. Few additional measures beyond directive’s scope.

While the legal and institutional frameworks governing nuclear safety and waste management across the EU are largely shaped by Euratom directives and international standards, the specific approaches taken by each MS are also deeply influenced by their individual nuclear histories. The evolution of national nuclear programs — whether early and expansive or late and limited — has played a crucial role in shaping both the urgency and the form of domestic waste policies. These historical trajectories have created significant variations in infrastructure, regulatory maturity, and political commitment, ultimately informing the way MS have interpreted and implemented EU requirements. Understanding this historical context is important to understand the divergence in national frameworks and the distinct paths countries have followed in developing waste strategies, especially regarding long-term disposal and decommissioning.

Historical Development of Nuclear Programs

The timing and scale of nuclear development has shaped national waste policies. Countries like France and the UK (when an EU member) pursued early nuclear weapons and power programs, leading to the construction of reprocessing plants and centralized waste strategies. In contrast, Sweden enacted a 1970s moratorium on new reactors unless an “absolutely safe” waste solution was in place — prompting a strong legal commitment to geological disposal. Similarly, Finland embedded strict disposal requirements into its national law.

Germany’s policy evolved under public pressure, with opposition to reprocessing and storage sites such as Wackersdorf and Gorleben shaping legislation toward prompt

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

disposal and a full nuclear phase-out. In Eastern Europe, Soviet legacy arrangements — such as spent fuel take-back agreements — delayed domestic repository development. When these agreements ended in the 2000s, affected countries had to rapidly establish national frameworks, often starting regulatory work much later than their Western counterparts. These varied historical experiences created distinct legal and technical trajectories across MS.

Legal and Institutional Frameworks

Each MS's legal system structures its approach to nuclear regulation differently. Some countries, like Finland, use a single comprehensive Nuclear Energy Act covering all nuclear activities, including waste management. Others have dedicated radioactive waste laws, e.g., France's 2006 Planning Act or Sweden's Act on Nuclear Activities and Financing.

These different approaches lead to divergences in:

- Definitions and classification of radioactive waste (e.g., France uses categories like Very Low-Level Waste (VLLW), Low-Level Waste, LLW, Intermediate-Level Waste (ILW), High-Level Waste (HLW); Spain uses categories I-IV; Sweden treats even very small lab samples as controlled nuclear waste).
- Institutional arrangements (centralized agencies like Andra in France vs. utility-led systems in others).
- Licensing procedures and the role of the regulator (some countries assign nuclear safety authorities' full oversight; others separate environmental permitting).

While most national systems are broadly compatible with IAEA standards, these dissimilarities complicate cross-border waste transfers and collaboration.

Policy and Societal Factors

National energy policies—especially commitments to nuclear expansion or phase-out—deeply influence waste regulation. Countries planning to grow their nuclear fleet

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

(e.g., Poland) may streamline licensing and invest in R&D, while phase-out countries (e.g., Germany, Belgium up until 2024) focus on decommissioning and long-term waste isolation.

Public opinion also plays a role. In federal countries like Germany and Belgium, regional opposition to siting facilities has necessitated more transparent and participatory processes. Differences in how MS have transposed EU directives contribute to regulatory divergence — not only in timing, but also in how national frameworks reflect EU-level objectives. In some cases, these differences have led to questions about consistency and completeness of implementation and have prompted further scrutiny at the EU level [6].

Finally, policies toward innovation differ: some countries prioritize proven methods, while others support advanced technologies like partitioning & transmutation (France) or future reactor types that could reduce waste volumes (Belgium). These choices affect how future-oriented and adaptive each national framework is.

In summary, despite shared EU directives and a common goal of safe waste disposal, MS's frameworks remain diverse shaped by historical paths, legal norms, and political choices.

3.4 The Role of International Standards

International cooperation is important for ensuring the safe decommissioning of nuclear facilities and the management of radioactive waste. Over the past decades, a framework of organizations and agreements has emerged to align and harmonize standards and regulations across countries. This section of the report provides a brief overview of the roles and collaborative efforts of key international bodies in this harmonization process. It examines how European and global institutions (from regulatory groups and treaties to technical agencies) work together to develop common safety standards, influence national policies, and share best practices in nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste management.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

3.4.1 European Nuclear Safety Regulators Group (ENSREG)

The European Nuclear Safety Regulators Group (ENSREG), established in 2007 and composed of senior regulators from all EU member states, is an independent advisory body to the EC. Its core mission is to promote high standards and a common understanding of nuclear safety, radioactive waste management, and decommissioning across the EU. ENSREG operates through specialized working groups and plays a key role in coordinating peer reviews (such as Topical Peer Reviews and EU stress tests) and supporting international safety initiatives like IRRS and ARTEMIS, fostering benchmarking and continuous improvement among national regulators.

ENSREG has significantly shaped EU policy, notably advising on the 2011 Council Directive on spent fuel and radioactive waste management, emphasizing principles like national responsibility, transparency, and public involvement. It continues to guide the EC on decommissioning, reactor life extension, and emergency preparedness. Through its working groups and plenary meetings, ENSREG promotes policy alignment and information exchange, contributing to harmonized safety standards. It also prioritizes transparency by publishing review findings, engaging stakeholders, and hosting public events to build public trust and encourage consistent regulatory practices.

3.4.2 International Conventions and Treaties

The Joint Convention on the Safety of Spent Fuel Management and on the Safety of Radioactive Waste Management [6], adopted in 1997 and in force since 2001, is the key international legal framework governing nuclear decommissioning and waste. It establishes binding obligations for over 85 contracting parties, requiring them to develop national frameworks, policies, and regulatory systems that ensure the safe management of radioactive waste and spent fuel. The Convention promotes high safety standards through international cooperation, transparency, and a robust peer-review process in which countries submit reports and receive feedback at periodic Review Meetings. Though non-enforceable, this peer-driven model encourages continuous improvement, fosters alignment with international norms, and strengthens national safety cultures.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

The Convention has significantly influenced national policies, prompting legal reforms, stronger regulatory bodies, and more comprehensive waste strategies. Its impact is especially notable in the European Union, where its principles are embedded in Euratom Directive 2011/70. It also sets conditions for transboundary waste movement, requiring recipient countries to have proper handling capacities. Complemented by other agreements like the Convention on Nuclear Safety and the Basel Convention, the Joint Convention forms part of a broader IAEA-led global framework. Despite some limitations—such as non-binding implementation and confidentiality in peer reviews — it remains a powerful tool for harmonizing international standards and encouraging progress, particularly among countries with emerging nuclear programs.

3.4.3 International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA)

The IAEA is the leading international body advancing regulatory harmonization in nuclear safety, particularly for decommissioning and radioactive waste management. It sets globally recognized safety standards — like GSR Part 5 (predisposal) and GSR Part 6 (decommissioning) — which, though not legally binding, serve as reference points for national regulators and reflect international consensus. To support adoption, the IAEA runs training initiatives, such as the 2025 School of Drafting Regulations, helping countries — especially those with emerging programs — translate these standards into national law. This effort ensures consistent safety practices across borders, even among states with differing regulatory maturity.

Beyond standard-setting, the IAEA reinforces harmonization through peer reviews and technical support. Services like ARTEMIS and IRRS allow countries to benchmark their frameworks and receive expert feedback based on IAEA guidance, aligning national systems with international expectations. These reviews also foster mutual learning and consistent improvement. The IAEA's Technical Cooperation program further supports convergence by building regulatory capacity and facilitating practical exchanges through expert missions and global networks like the International Decommissioning Network. While adoption remains voluntary, the IAEA's moral authority, collaborative platforms, and persistent updates to reflect best practices make it a powerful driver of regulatory alignment worldwide.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

3.4.4 OECD/Nuclear Energy Agency (NEA)

The OECD Nuclear Energy Agency (NEA) plays a substantial role in regulatory harmonization among advanced nuclear nations, focusing on deep technical, policy, and legal coordination in decommissioning and radioactive waste management. Through expert forums like the Radioactive Waste Management Committee (RWMC) and the Committee on Decommissioning (CDLM), the NEA fosters alignment by developing shared concepts —such as the "Safety Case" for geological repositories — and coordinating joint research on topics like waste form behaviour and dismantling techniques. These initiatives help OECD member states adopt best practices, harmonize regulatory philosophies, and address complex policy challenges collaboratively.

The NEA also contributes to harmonization through consensus-building publications, peer reviews, and high-level policy dialogues. By issuing collective statements and technical reports and organizing expert reviews of national projects the NEA enables countries to benchmark and refine their regulatory approaches. Its influence is particularly visible in the convergence of decommissioning planning and waste disposal strategies among its 33 member states. Although its scope is limited to developed countries, NEA's work complements broader IAEA efforts and often feeds into global standards, indirectly supporting worldwide regulatory alignment through publicly available guidance and inter-agency collaboration.

3.4.5 Western European Nuclear Regulators Association (WENRA)

The Western European Nuclear Regulators Association (WENRA) is a voluntary network of European nuclear regulators dedicated to regulatory harmonization in nuclear safety, particularly in radioactive waste management and decommissioning. Its primary tool is the development of Safety Reference Levels (SRLs) — a set of minimum common requirements that WENRA members have formally committed to implement within their national regulatory frameworks, with the goal of achieving harmonized safety standards across member countries [8]. Through its Working Group on Waste and Decommissioning (WGWD), WENRA has developed multiple sets of Safety Reference Levels (SRLs), based on IAEA standards and tailored to reflect European regulatory practices. These SRLs cover processing, storage, disposal, and

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

decommissioning, and serve as a shared benchmark for high regulatory standards across Europe.

WENRA's harmonization process is systematic and peer-driven: regulators self-assess their national frameworks against each SRL and score them using a standardized method (“A”, “B”, or “C”), with mandatory action plans for non-compliance [9]. Peer reviews and plenary discussions validate these results, and progress is tracked publicly. This process has driven regulatory upgrades even in advanced countries and has aligned national practices toward a common European baseline. WENRA's work is closely coordinated with ENSREG and the EC (SRLs have influenced EU directives) and complements IAEA efforts by enabling faster updates and region-specific refinements [10]. While its standards are not legally binding, WENRA plays a significant role in shaping harmonized nuclear safety regulation and offers an alignment mechanism that could inform global practices.

3.5 Complementarity and Overlap Among International Efforts

Despite the involvement of multiple organizations in nuclear decommissioning and waste management regulation, their efforts toward regulatory harmonization are largely complementary, not conflicting. Each organization operates within a distinct geographical and functional scope, creating a layered and interconnected system. WENRA and ENSREG focus on Europe, driving harmonization through technical SRLs and EU law, while the IAEA and Joint Convention provide global standards and legal accountability. The OECD/NEA bridges these levels by convening developed countries to solve complex technical and policy issues. Overlapping membership and regular collaboration ensure coherence—IAEA standards feed into WENRA's SRLs, NEA findings inform IAEA reviews, and ENSREG uses IAEA tools like ARTEMIS to fulfil EU legal mandates.

This division of labour enables synergy: the IAEA sets broad standards and offers peer reviews, the Joint Convention compels state-level reporting and benchmarking, NEA facilitates high-level technical consensus, WENRA defines regulatory expectations and ENSREG connects these to EU policy and enforcement. Formal coordination mechanisms — such as joint meetings, shared participation, and reciprocal use of peer

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

review results — help manage potential duplication and streamline national obligations. While administrative burden remains a challenge, particularly for smaller states, the multi-actor system ultimately reinforces key safety principles. Rather than conflicting mandates, the overlapping efforts send a unified message: converging national regulations with international best practices is essential for safe, credible, and transparent nuclear decommissioning and waste management.

3.6 Effectiveness, Challenges, and Gaps in Harmonization

International cooperation through the IAEA, Joint Convention, OECD/NEA, WENRA, and ENSREG has led to steady progress in harmonizing safety requirements and regulatory expectations for nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste management. There is now wide agreement on key principles — such as the need to plan for decommissioning from the start of a facility’s life and to use geological disposal for high-level waste. Most countries with nuclear programs have set up laws and systems that follow the standards set by these international bodies. In Europe, binding EU directives and WENRA’s Safety Reference Levels have helped ensure that countries apply the same safety rules. Peer review processes like IRRS and ARTEMIS, and expert networks from the NEA and IAEA, have helped countries learn from each other and improve their systems. These efforts have also helped countries with less experience to build up the skills and tools they need to meet international expectations.

Despite this progress, some gaps remain. International standards are not legally binding unless countries choose to formally incorporate them into national legislation, meaning that continued progress ultimately depends on political commitment. Moreover, even when regulations are aligned with international standards on paper, some countries still face significant challenges in practice, lacking the financial resources, skilled personnel, or technical capacity needed for full implementation. New technical challenges are also emerging, such as the decommissioning of advanced reactors and the remediation of legacy uranium mining and milling sites in regions like Central Asia and Eastern Europe, where deteriorating waste containment structures pose significant environmental and health risks [11]. In some cases, countries interpret key terms differently—for example, in how they classify waste—which makes cross-border cooperation more difficult. Public involvement is another area where practices

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

vary widely, and there is no international standard for how to engage communities or gain public trust. While this does not directly affect safety rules, it can slow or block progress.

In summary, the international system has done a good job of creating common goals and supporting countries in reaching them. But turning shared standards into consistent results still requires work, especially in helping all countries build capacity and keep up with new developments.

Clearly international and European organisations play an important role in supporting how EU countries apply nuclear safety and waste management rules. Each organisation has a different function — some focus on setting safety standards, while others coordinate reviews, share technical knowledge, or support EU-level oversight. The figure below shows how these organisations — IAEA, NEA, WENRA, and ENSREG — work with MS and with each other. Their combined efforts help ensure that national systems are consistent, safe, and based on shared practices.

Figure 1 shows how international and European bodies — IAEA, NEA, WENRA, the Joint Convention, and ENSREG — interact with EU Member States to support the development and implementation of Euratom directives. Each plays a distinct role: the IAEA sets global standards; the Joint Convention establishes international obligations; the NEA fosters technical alignment; WENRA adapts IAEA guidance into European Safety Reference Levels; and ENSREG links these inputs to EU law and regulatory oversight. Together, they promote consistency, transparency, and continuous improvement in nuclear safety, decommissioning, and radioactive waste management.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

Figure 1: Coordination of International and European Bodies in Supporting Euratom Directives.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

3.7 HARPERS Areas of Interest

3.7.1 Cross border services / facilities

With the broader legal and institutional landscape now established — including the roles of key international and European bodies in shaping regulatory approaches — the report now narrows its focus to the three core thematic areas identified by the HARPERS project. These are: Cross-Border Services and Facilities (WP3), Circular Economy (WP4), and Advanced Technologies (WP5). A set of topics were further distilled from these thematic areas which brought forward some purported regulatory challenges and opportunities for greater alignment within the EU. The following sections draw on the findings of the upstream work packages to assess whether the identified issues are regulatory in nature, where differences between national approaches may pose obstacles, and how alignment — whether formal or through shared practices — could support safer, more efficient, and innovation-friendly decommissioning and waste management across MS.

Cross-Border Waste Management refers to situations where radioactive waste or spent fuel is shipped across national boundaries for treatment, storage, or (potentially) disposal. Nuclear materials are routinely transported for commercial reasons — for example, sending spent fuel to France for reprocessing or to Cyclife for treatment, with the resulting vitrified or residue wastes being returned to the country of origin. However, questions remain as to whether EU regulatory frameworks align sufficiently to allow the most efficient use of such cross-border services. There is also the possibility of shared disposal facilities to be considered, particularly for smaller countries with limited disposal capacity, such as Slovenia, Slovakia, or the Baltic states. Initiatives such as the ERDO association (European Repository Development Organisation) illustrate how regional cooperation is being explored in this context.

- **Current Practices:** Cross-border services in the EU have included fuel reprocessing contracts. Spain, Germany, Belgium, Italy, the Netherlands, and others have shipped spent fuel to the UK or France under commercial contracts[12] [13], with some arrangements (such as those involving the Netherlands) still ongoing. These services also involve shipments of radioactive

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

waste for treatment, particularly when a country, such as Finland or Spain, lacks specific waste management capabilities. For example, metallic waste from nuclear facilities in Finland, the UK, Germany, Spain, and other EU countries has been shipped to Cyclife Sweden AB (formerly part of Studsvik), where it is treated at the Nyköping facility through processes such as decontamination, incineration, and metal melting. These activities are governed by the Shipment Directive (2006/117/Euratom), which sets a common system of prior approvals for transboundary movements [14]. Under this system, an exporting country must obtain consent from the receiving country's authorities; all EU states have designated authorities for this procedure. In practice, waste shipments occur regularly within the EU and the regulatory process is well-established. For instance, the directive explicitly allows shipment of spent fuel to another MS for reprocessing, with the condition that resulting waste is taken back. This has enabled a form of service trade (France, and until recently the UK, as providers; others as clients) [15].

- **Divergent National Rules:** Divergent National Rules: Despite the common EU framework, national laws vary on whether they permit or prohibit certain cross-border arrangements — particularly for the final disposal of radioactive waste. In contrast, cross-border arrangements for waste treatment and interim storage are generally less restricted and have proceeded with fewer legal obstacles. Some countries have legal prohibitions on importing foreign nuclear waste for disposal – Finland [16] and Sweden [17] each have laws banning import of foreign spent fuel or waste, reflecting public and political insistence that their repositories serve national needs only. In contrast, Belgium has shown openness by agreeing to potentially take Luxembourg's waste [18], and Slovakia at one point indicated willingness to consider hosting a regional spent fuel storage facility for neighbouring countries (though not realized) [19]. Likewise, exporting waste for disposal is forbidden by some national policies (Germany's law, for example, forbids exporting spent fuel for final disposal – Germany must dispose of its waste on its own soil) [20], whereas others explicitly allow export if it meets EU conditions (many smaller countries wrote this into their national programs as a contingency) [19]. These legal differences

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

could pose an obstacle if the EU were to pursue a more integrated repository approach. For a multinational repository to be viable, the host country must legally allow imports, while client countries must authorise exports. Such import/export agreements have been realised in the case of treatment and interim storage.

- **Harmonization Needs:** To promote cross-border facilities (such as a shared European repository or regional storage centre), further alignment in several areas may be beneficial:
 - **Liability and Oversight:** Countries assign regulatory oversight to different bodies; a shared facility might need a joint regulatory framework or mutual recognition of safety standards. Aligning safety requirements (e.g., waste package standards, transportation cask criteria) helps ensure all parties are confident in each other's regulation. WENRA has developed reference safety standards for waste disposal facilities – broad adoption of these can harmonize expectations.
 - **Waste Classification and Acceptance Criteria:** Waste classification systems and acceptance criteria vary across EU MS, reflecting differences in national regulatory frameworks and facility-specific safety cases. While these differences rarely pose a technical barrier to cross-border movement, they can require additional administrative effort, particularly when transferring waste for treatment, storage, or disposal. An EU study found that although differences exist, most countries did not consider their classification schemes a serious obstacle to export/import; however, a few (including Estonia, Bulgaria, Finland, and Sweden) noted that translating categories required effort [21]. Waste acceptance criteria (WAC), in contrast, are inherently site-specific and derived from the design and safety case of each facility, making harmonization impractical. Instead, future cooperation could focus on guidance or shared methodologies for how WAC are developed. Regardless of national classifications, the burden of compliance lies entirely with the sender, who must ensure that the waste meets the host country's classification and WAC. Further progress in mapping national

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

classification schemes — potentially referencing the IAEA’s generalized system — could also support cross-border predisposal activities, not just disposal.

- *Procedural Streamlining:* The current shipment authorization process under the EU framework functions well, it can be time-consuming and bureaucratic. As cross-border services grow — such as in the context of waste treatment from decommissioning activities — there may be value in more streamlined or multilateral arrangements. In fact, regional treatment centres already exist, such as Cyclife Sweden AB, which receives and processes metallic waste from multiple EU countries. While these services operate within the current regulatory framework, broader use may benefit from more efficient authorizations. One example of formalized cooperation is the 2016 Belgium–Luxembourg agreement, which defines conditions for the disposal of Luxembourg’s radioactive waste in Belgium and avoids case-by-case shipment approvals. Although focused on disposal, the agreement provides a potential model for future framework arrangements between interested MS, whether for treatment, storage, or disposal.

Overall, regulatory alignment in cross-border radioactive waste management is moderate but not complete. The basic legal ability to engage in such cooperation exists EU-wide under common rules, but differences in national laws — such as import/export bans — and administrative hurdles continue to pose challenges. Given that at least a dozen EU countries foresee shared solutions in their national plans [22] , including joint repositories, regional treatment centres, or shared interim storage, there is a clear case for strengthening legal and procedural coordination to enable these initiatives.

In conclusion on this point, further alignment — such as through EU-supported agreements or guidance on how national authorities manage approvals — could support more cost-effective regional solutions, while respecting national safety standards and sovereignty. This would not require all countries to participate. However, providing a clear and legally supported pathway for those that wish to share facilities

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

could be helpful. In all cases, the sender would still be required to fully comply with the host country's acceptance criteria.

3.7.2 Circular Economy in Decommissioning (Material Reuse)

Transitioning to circular economy strategies is a growing focus even in the nuclear industry. Decommissioning a nuclear facility yields large volumes of materials (concrete, steel, equipment) that are potentially reusable or recyclable. Reusing or recycling as much material as possible can reduce the amount that must be disposed of as radioactive waste [23]. As such, not only can the environmental burden be lessened, but disposal costs as well. However, national regulations differ on how—and in some cases whether—such materials can be cleared and allowed to re-enter the economy, which leads to regulatory divergence

- **Regulatory Approaches to Clearance:** Most countries have a concept of “clearance levels” – thresholds below which material is no longer regulated as radioactive and can be recycled or disposed of as conventional waste. The EU's Basic Safety Standards (Directive 2013/59/Euratom) sets recommended clearance levels for common radionuclides, such as 0.01 mSv/year for general clearance, providing some degree of uniformity. In practice, many countries have incorporated these or similar levels into their regulations, but implementation varies. For instance, Germany may allow slightly contaminated concrete rubble to be cleared for use as road fill or landfill cover, whereas France might require that same material to be disposed of in a radioactive waste repository due to more conservative clearance frameworks and public concern. Furthermore, differences in clearance criteria and procedures can hinder cross-border reuse of materials. For example, if metal from a decommissioned reactor in Country A is treated and cleared, it may only be sold as scrap in Country B if Country B accepts the clearance methodology and results. A recent EU survey highlighted that regulatory differences regarding clearance of materials still remain an issue; it recommended sharing experiences among MS and evaluating the potential benefits of more harmonized approaches [24]. While mutual recognition is complex in practice, the overarching goal is to ensure that materials meeting defined low-risk criteria can be safely reused, with greater

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

regulatory clarity and cost-efficiency across borders. Cost reduction remains a major driver for the adoption of clearance and reuse strategies.

- **Current Divergence:** Some countries, notably Germany, have actively recycled decommissioned materials, such as slightly radioactive steel and concrete, following decontamination. This process is conducted under strict clearance limits, measured in microsieverts (μSv) of potential exposure, and oversight. Sweden and Finland also have established clearance processes. In contrast, other programs have been more restrictive. France, for example, historically did not have a provision for unconditional clearance of very low-level material; instead, a category of VLLW was created for which the waste disposed in dedicated landfills rather than released to the market. This policy choice was made partly to maintain public confidence that no “radioactive” material ends up in consumer products. The UK had instances of *radioactively contaminated metal recycling* that led to public alarm in the 1990s, influencing more cautious policies. Thus, even among EU members, attitudes range from proactively embracing recycling of decommissioned materials to a preference for disposal to avoid any risk of radioactive material circulation.
- **Need for Alignment:** As the nuclear fleet ages, decommissioning waste volumes will increase across Europe, possibly making circular economy approaches more attractive. Greater alignment could involve:
 - **Standardized Clearance Levels:** Ensuring all MS adopt the same clearance thresholds (e.g., those in EU/BSS or IAEA guidelines) and measurement methodologies allowing cleared material from one country to be more readily acceptable in another. The EC could update guidance or even a regulation to solidify common clearance standards [25], [26].
 - **Mutual Recognition Agreements:** Countries could formally agree to recognize each other’s clearance certificates for materials thereby facilitating cross-border recycling markets for steel, copper, etc., recovered from nuclear sites [27].
 - **Sharing Best Practices:** Some states have developed advanced techniques (e.g., Sweden’s waste authority and steel industry collaboration to melt scrap from decommissioning into recycled steel).

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

Others could benefit from guidance on how to set up such clearance and monitoring programs. An EU-level forum or technical body could issue best practice guidelines on material reuse, including aspects like record-keeping (digital tracking of cleared batches), stakeholder communication (to build trust in recycled materials), and areas to avoid (i.e., consumer products instead focusing on industrial reuse to avoid public perception issues) [28], [29].

- Addressing Public Perception: Even if regulations align, the public in each country must accept the concept. Harmonization efforts should include transparency and public engagement strategies – for example, clearly explaining that cleared material poses no more radiation risk than natural background. The PREDIS project’s Strategic Research Agenda notes the “*need for societal engagement for recycling*” alongside harmonizing practices.

All EU countries strive to minimize waste, and many allow some reuse of decommissioning materials. Inconsistent rules may impede the full breadth of a truly circular approach. Aligning regulations in this domain would promote resource efficiency EU-wide.

Therefore, further coordination (potentially an EU directive focusing on decommissioning material management or an extension of circular economy policy to the nuclear sector) may be beneficial and is indeed being discussed in expert circles [30].

3.7.3 Advanced Technologies: Robotics, BIM, and Digital Twins

The nuclear decommissioning and waste management field is being potentially transformed by advanced technologies – including robotics for remote handling, drones for surveying, BIM for planning, and digital twin simulations of nuclear facilities. These technologies are intended to improve safety (by, e.g., reducing human exposure), increase efficiency, and enhance documentation. However, regulatory uptake varies across the EU. Key points of divergence and the case for alignment include:

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

- **Adoption in Practice**: Countries with large decommissioning projects have pioneered use of robotics and digital tools. For example, in the UK [31] and France [32], [33], robots have been used to inspect and dismantle highly contaminated equipment (UK's Sellafield cleanup has a dedicated National Centre for Nuclear Robotics, though the UK is now outside EU). Belgium and Germany have used remotely operated vehicles in reactor vessel segmentation. Digital tools, including DT and BIM, are being tested to optimize decommissioning workflows in several countries. For example, national agencies such as Italy's SOGIN (in research reactor dismantling) and organizations in Finland are developing digital models to support dismantling operations. These approaches aim to improve planning, simulation, and monitoring by creating dynamic virtual representations of physical assets and operations. The broader application of 3D simulation and virtual reality tools in nuclear decommissioning has also been demonstrated in international projects [34]. The IAEA has highlighted how drones, AI, and DT are already helping advance decommissioning projects globally [35], [36], and is currently coordinating the collaborative project NET4D [37], which aims to share international experience and will produce a dedicated TECDOC. An EU research initiative (the EURAD program) also emphasizes integrating "Industry 4.0" technologies into waste management [38], [39], [40].
- **Regulatory Acceptance** [41], [42]: One divergence lies in how regulators view these innovations. While traditional nuclear regulations did not explicitly address digital twin models or autonomous robots, regulatory frameworks are progressively considering these technologies. Ongoing discussions and research aim to develop appropriate guidelines and standards to ensure their safe and effective integration into nuclear operations. Some national regulators are proactive [43] – for instance, France's ASN [44] have shown openness to using BIM models as part of decommissioning license submissions (e.g. requiring 3D models to illustrate dismantling plans) In Italy, it is mandatory for public entities such as SOGIN to adopt BIM for decommissioning project design and tender preparation, for construction or refurbishment contracts valued over

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

1 million euros, starting from January 2025. Others may not formally require or evaluate such tools yet. There is also the question of standards [45]:

- How to qualify a robotic system for nuclear use?
- How to ensure a digital simulation is accurate enough for safety decisions?
- If one country's regulator develops guidelines on this (say, the use of a digital twin for waste package inventory verification) [46], [47], [48], it would be efficient if others adopted similar standards so technology providers can design to a common specification. Coordination via WENRA or ENSREG could help create reference guidance on digital technologies in nuclear decommissioning.
- **Examples of Divergence:** Use of BIM for regulatory submissions: the UK and Finland have used 3D BIM models to support safety case reviews, but another country might still be using only paper or 2D drawings. These inconsistencies mean companies working across borders face different expectations and cannot uniformly apply best available technologies.
- **Harmonization Opportunities:** Advanced technologies are an area where *sharing knowledge and aligning standards* can accelerate improvement for all:
 - The EU (through Euratom research) is already funding joint projects to demonstrate robotics and remote systems. A 2021 OECD/NEA report also identified common barriers and cost-benefits of robotic systems in nuclear waste tasks [49]. Using such analyses, regulators could agree on common safety criteria for robotics (covering reliability, fail-safes, radiation tolerance, etc.). This would give vendors a clear target and reassure all regulators of their safety.
 - For BIM and digital twins, developing EU-level guidelines on digital information management in nuclear projects would help. For example, an EU guidance might encourage that decommissioning projects use BIM to map radiological inventory, which regulators could then review. If every regulator expects a “digital twin” of a complex facility, it becomes a de facto standard.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

- Training and knowledge transfer [50]: Embracing advanced technology also means training regulators and operators in their use. Through ENSREG or the IAEA, EU states can participate in training exercises (for instance, virtual reality training for inspectors, or workshops on interpreting digital twin data). The EU JRC has organized a Decommissioning and Waste Management Summer School that in 2019 included such topics illustrating the value of cross-European education.

In essence, while advanced technologies are being introduced, their deployment risks being slowed by a fragmented, country-by-country approach. Given the clear benefits — such as improved safety, accuracy, and potential cost savings — it would be advantageous to pursue greater regulatory coordination. This would not necessarily require new binding EU legislation. Instead, alignment could be achieved through 'soft harmonization,' i.e., the voluntary development of shared guidelines, best practices, and reference standards that Member States agree to apply consistently.

In summary, advanced technology usage is an area where EU-wide collaboration and alignment can ensure all countries benefit from innovation and no country's regulations unnecessarily impede modern best practices.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

4 Methodology

4.1 Introduction

This chapter outlines the methodology used in Work Package 6 (WP6) to assess and interpret the regulatory challenges identified across the upstream work packages of the HARPERS project. The analysis presented here builds on the structured findings of WP3 (Cross-Border Services), WP4 (Circular Economy), and WP5 (Advanced Technologies), which were summarised in dedicated memos and informed by stakeholder input, technical assessments, and literature reviews. WP6 focused on synthesising and classifying the identified issues using a structured decision-tree framework. Each issue was examined to determine whether its root cause was regulatory, technical, strategic, or perceptual in nature. Expert contributions from SURO and ASNR provided additional insight to ensure accuracy and relevance across MS contexts. A more detailed discussion of the upstream findings and supporting evidence can be found in Appendices A, B, and C, corresponding to WP3, WP4, and WP5 respectively.

4.2 WP6-Specific Analysis Methodology

The WP6 analysis drew primarily on a synthesis of findings from the three preceding work packages — WP3 (Cross-Border Services), WP4 (Circular Economy), and WP5 (Advanced Technologies). A key milestone from each of these work packages was the production of a structured memo, also referred to as a regulatory framework and criteria report. These documents summarized the main challenges identified through surveys, stakeholder consultations, and technical assessments, and served as the foundation for WP6's regulatory analysis.

The WP6 team systematically extracted and compiled the relevant findings from these documents, with particular focus on instances that were explicitly or implicitly regulatory in nature. A targeted literature review was conducted to contextualize and supplement these findings, with emphasis on existing EU directives, national transposition practices, and relevant international standards (e.g., from WENRA and the IAEA).

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

To strengthen the analysis, expert input was provided by SURO (Czech Republic), GRS (Germany) and ASNR (France), who supported both the interpretation of the extracted findings and the formulation of alignment strategies. This input was particularly valuable in assessing the regulatory significance of certain issues and ensuring that the report's conclusions reflected practical realities in different MS contexts.

Overall, the analysis relied on existing data sources, partner expertise, and established guidance materials to ensure a focused and proportionate evaluation of regulatory alignment challenges.

4.2.1 Classification Framework for Problem Statements

This section outlines the classification system used by WP6 to interpret and organise the regulatory challenges identified across WP3, WP4, and WP5.

The classification was carried out collaboratively by VTT (Work Package Lead), GRS and VTT (Advanced Technologies), SURO (Subtask Leader – Cross-Border Services), and ASNR (Subtask Leader – Circular Economy and Advanced Technologies). Their combined expertise ensured that the classification of problem statements reflected both regulatory nuance and practical operational experience across multiple MSMS.

The goal of this framework was to systematically categorise issues into one of four defined classes — Regulatory Issues, Technical Issues, Strategic Issues, or Perceived Issues — and to ensure that each classification was consistent with international standards. Where appropriate, validation was carried out using WENRA Safety Reference Levels (SRLs) and IAEA guidance documents.

4.2.2 Refined Classes for Problem Statements

The classification framework defines four main categories, each with clear characteristics and purposes, to address the diverse issues in nuclear waste management.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

4.2.2.1 Regulatory Issues

These refer to challenges arising from legal frameworks, regulatory structures, or compliance mechanisms that could possibly benefit from clarification, harmonisation, or reform. Regulatory issues typically involve differences between national and international standards or possibly outdated legal provisions that impede implementation.

Examples:

- Divergent licensing requirements for cross-border waste facilities.
- Lack of guidance on digital tools within regulatory frameworks.
- Inconsistent definitions of radioactive waste categories.

4.2.2.2 Technical Issues

These relate to engineering, scientific, or operational barriers. While not inherently regulatory, they often impact regulatory compliance or create friction in implementation. In some cases, technical issues are interpreted as regulatory due to effects on practical feasibility.

Examples:

- Limitations in decontamination technologies for circular economy reuse.
- Technical gaps in material clearance measurement or classification.
- Integration challenges for robotics and BIM in legacy facilities.

4.2.2.3 Strategic Issues

Strategic issues emerge from broader planning or governance challenges. These concern how decisions are prioritised at policy or organisational levels, including allocation of resources, infrastructure planning, and cross-border collaboration. Strategic issues are often interlinked to both regulatory and technical contexts.

Examples:

- Lack of coordinated EU-level strategy for shared disposal facilities.
- Uncertainty in prioritising circular economy investments vs. compliance goals.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

- Disparate national approaches to innovation adoption in regulation.

4.2.2.4 Perceived Issues

Perceived issues are problems initially framed as regulatory, technical, or strategic, but which upon closer inspection are driven by misinterpretations, incomplete information, or contextual misunderstandings. Identifying them helps avoid misdirected solutions and encourages clearer communication.

Examples:

- Believing a delay in transport licensing is due to EU law, when it is caused by missing technical documentation.
- Attributing clearance rejection to national bias rather than diverging measurement assumptions.

4.2.3 Analytical Tools and Techniques Used

Issue classification followed a structured three-step process:

2. **Initial Interpretation:**

Each issue was extracted from the WP3–5 regulatory framework and criteria reports and initially categorised based on how it was presented by the original work package team.

3. **Root Cause Analysis:**

WP6 analysts—supported by literature review and expert partners—examined each issue’s underlying cause. Questions included: Does this arise from legislation, technical constraints, or policy-level decision-making?

4. **Validation Against Standards:**

Final classifications were reviewed against the WENRA SRLs and relevant IAEA publications to ensure alignment with recognised international benchmarks.

This approach provided an additional layer of scrutiny and supported a methodical evaluation of each issue, drawing on structured evidence, prior stakeholder input, and expert interpretation.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

4.2.4 Framework for Classification

The decision tree presented in Figure 2 outlines the step-by-step process applied in WP6 to classify problem statements derived from WP3 to WP5. Beginning with the initial review of each issue, the process guides the analyst through a sequence of targeted questions addressing legal, technical, strategic, and perceptual dimensions. At each stage, validation is supported by references to international standards (e.g., WENRA, IAEA) and expert judgement from WP6 partners. This structured approach ensured a consistent and transparent categorisation process consistent with the overall goals of regulatory alignment.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

Figure 2: Structured approach used in WP6 to categorise issues as regulatory, technical, strategic, or perceived based on evidence and expert validation.

5 Results and Discussion

5.1 Introduction

This section presents the results of the regulatory impact assessments carried out under Work Packages 3, 4, and 5 of the HARPERS project. Drawing on stakeholder input, case studies, and technical reviews, a range of potential regulatory issues were identified relating to waste classification and treatment, circular economy implementation, and the use of advanced technologies in nuclear waste management decommissioning. To support clarity and comparability, the issues have been grouped into thematic clusters based on their underlying characteristics. Each issue has then been classified as regulatory, strategic, technical, or perceived, following a structured decision-tree methodology developed within the project. This classification allows for a clearer distinction between actual regulatory barriers and challenges rooted in implementation, interpretation, or a lack of supporting guidance. While this section provides a summary of the key findings, full analysis, detailed arguments, and supporting evidence can be found in Appendices A, B, and C, which correspond to the outputs of WP3, WP4, and WP5 respectively.

5.2 Regulatory Impact on the Alignment of Wastes with Treatment Technologies

The regulatory issues discussed in this section are based on findings from Milestone 20: Evaluating Harmonization of Individual EU and International Countries' Problematic Waste Inventory, developed under the HARPERS project by Task 3.2b. Drawing on stakeholder questionnaires and case studies across multiple EU MS, the report identified nine issues as being regulatory in nature. These arise in areas such as waste classification, regulatory frameworks, and cross-border cooperation.

To support clearer analysis, the identified issues were grouped into thematic clusters based on their underlying characteristics. This clustering approach distinguishes between conceptual (e.g., how terms are defined), structural (e.g., national classification systems), procedural (e.g., permitting and regulatory scope), and coordination differences. Grouping in this way allows related issues to be examined

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

collectively, particularly where shared root causes suggest that integrated solutions may be possible.

Table 2: Regulatory issues identified in WP3: Summary of issues analysed under WP3, including descriptions, national examples, and thematic cluster assignments.

Issue No.	WP3 Issue Name	Description	Examples/Impacts	Cluster No.	Cluster Name
1	Lack of Unified Definition for Problematic Waste	No consistent national/internal definition across countries and organizations.	Hinders harmonization and inventory alignment; only UK and France have internal definitions.	1	Conceptual
2	Differences in National Waste Classification Standards	Countries follow varying classification frameworks (e.g., IAEA GSG-1 vs national standards).	Limits comparability, benchmarking, and coordinated treatment.	2	Classification Systems and Waste Acceptance
4	Legal and Administrative Barriers to Cross-Border Cooperation	Legislative permission for import/export exists in many MS, but implementation varies.	Room for improved communication and clarity; examples show cooperation is possible (e.g., La Hague).	3	Legal and Regulatory Frameworks
5	Lack of Harmonized Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC)	Some waste streams lack fully developed or harmonized WAC.	Perceived as a barrier but practical solutions exist (e.g., return of LILW from La Hague after spent fuel reprocessing).	2	Classification Systems and Waste Acceptance
8	Diverging Legal Interpretations of Hazardous RAW	MS apply differing legal approaches to radioactive vs hazardous waste.	Parallel vs. integrated regulation; calls for harmonized EU treatment.	1	Conceptual
9	Societal and Political Constraints on Waste Management	Political and public resistance affects prioritization of treatment infrastructure.	Public opposition, prioritization gaps, and regulator disengagement delay facility implementation.	4	Institutional Coordination and Participation
10	Lack of Treatment Infrastructure for Hazardous RAW	No established routes for certain hazardous RAW types.	Opportunity identified for joint facility development across Europe.	4	Institutional Coordination and Participation

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

5.2.1 Analysis of issues:

Table 3 summarizes the regulatory issues examined in the WP3 regulatory impact assessment, categorized according to their underlying nature — conceptual, structural, legal, or institutional. Each issue has been classified as a regulatory, strategic, technical, or perceived issue based on the decision-tree methodology described in the Section 4.2.4. The summary highlights the essential rationale for each classification, drawing directly from the findings presented in the WP3 milestone. This structured overview is intended to provide a concise yet comprehensive reference point for understanding the nature of the barriers affecting cross-border radioactive waste management. The full analysis underlying these classifications is provided in Appendix A.

Table 3: Classification of WP3 issues by type: Categorization of regulatory, strategic, technical, and perceived barriers based on structured methodology, with rationale for classification.

Cluster	Issue No.	Issue Title	Classification	Summary of Rationale
1. Conceptual	1	Lack of Unified Definition for Problematic Waste	Regulatory	Many countries lack internal/national definitions, leading to inconsistent interpretation and classification of problematic waste among stakeholders such as regulators, waste management organizations, and operators. A harmonized definition at the EU or international level could be beneficial.
	8	Diverging Legal Interpretations of Hazardous RAW	Regulatory	MS apply differing legal regimes to hazardous RAW (parallel vs integrated systems). Harmonization would reduce complexity and facilitate cooperation.
2. Classification Systems & Waste Acceptance	2	Differences in National Waste Classification Standards	Regulatory	Countries follow different classification standards (e.g., IAEA GSG-1 vs national guidance), limiting comparability and mutual understanding.
	5	Lack of Harmonized Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC)	Perceived	While Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC) may be missing for certain waste types at the disposal stage, this does not always prevent interim treatment. Real examples (e.g., La Hague) show that waste can be accepted for treatment under specific

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

				agreements, processed, and returned to the originator, even if final disposal WAC are not yet established.
3. Legal and Regulatory Frameworks	4	Legal and Administrative Barriers to Cross-Border Cooperation	Perceived	Many countries have legislation in place governing radioactive waste management and decommissioning, but issues arise from unclear interpretation or poor coordination, not from a lack of regulatory frameworks.
4. Institutional Coordination & Participation	9	Societal and Political Constraints on Waste Management	Strategic	Public opposition, unclear prioritization, and lack of regulator engagement contribute to delays and inconsistency in facility planning and cross-border efforts.
	10	Lack of Treatment Infrastructure for Hazardous RAW	Technical	Some types of hazardous RAW lack clear management routes. This represents an opportunity for joint development of facilities or common approaches.

5.2.2 Conclusion

The classification of issues presented in this section is based on the application of a decision-tree methodology to the findings reported in the WP3 milestone. The purpose of this approach was to identify whether the issues raised by stakeholders reflect regulatory obstacles, strategic challenges, technical limitations, or perceived barriers.

Only a limited number of issues were classified as regulatory. These primarily relate to the absence of harmonised definitions and classifications at the supra-national level, particularly with regard to problematic waste and hazardous radioactive waste. Without consistent frameworks and standards, collaboration between countries becomes more uncertain, potentially leading to inefficiencies, increased costs, and delays in the safe management of nuclear materials.

Other issues were classified as strategic, technical, or perceived. In several cases, challenges raised by stakeholders — such as the lack of Waste Acceptance Criteria or legal barriers to export/import — were found to reflect differences in interpretation or implementation, rather than the absence of regulatory provisions. Similarly, the lack of infrastructure or regulator engagement was considered to reflect national-level prioritisation or planning issues, rather than legal or technical constraints.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

The analysis also highlights the need importance of distinguishing between perceived barriers and actual regulatory framework limitations. Examples cited in the WP3 milestone, such as the operation of cross-border treatment facilities, indicate that cooperation is possible under existing frameworks in some cases.

Overall, the findings point to a need for greater clarity, coordination, and alignment of definitions and practices, while recognising that not all identified issues require regulatory solutions. In most cases, targeted guidance, clearer communication, and stronger collaboration among stakeholders could provide effective and efficient solutions.

5.3 WP4 Regulatory framework and criteria report

The regulatory issues presented in this section are based on findings from Milestone MS21 – WP4 Regulatory Framework and Criteria Report, developed under the HARPERS project. Drawing on stakeholder feedback and technical analysis, the report identifies ten challenges as being regulatory in nature and affecting the integration of circular economy principles into nuclear decommissioning practices. These challenges relate to areas such as clearance, reuse of materials, regulatory scope, and technical guidance.

To support clearer analysis, the identified issues were grouped into thematic clusters based on their underlying characteristics. This clustering approach distinguishes between issues of legal transposition and interpretation, procedural and operational burdens, gaps in regulatory scope and integration, and shortcomings in technical support tools and standards. Grouping in this way allows related issues to be considered collectively, particularly where common root causes suggest that solutions may be approached in a coordinated or systematic manner. Table 4 gives a summary of circular economy barriers analysed in WP4, including classification, underlying rationale, and issue clusters.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

Table 4: **Regulatory issues identified in WP4:** Summary of circular economy barriers analysed in WP4, including classification, underlying rationale, and issue clusters.

Issue No.	WP4 Issue Name	Description	Examples/Impacts	Cluster No.	Cluster Name
1	Inconsistent Transposition of EU Directive 2013/59	EU directive applied inconsistently across MS, creating legal divergence in clearance levels.	Creates cross-border inconsistency; some MS apply additional national conditions or surface contamination limits.	1	Legal Transposition and Interpretation
2	Overly Stringent and Non-Risk-Based Approaches	Some MS implement stricter requirements than possibly justified by risk levels, exceeding international benchmarks.	Leads to over-control and unnecessary cleanup; fails to adopt graded, risk-informed approaches.	1	Legal Transposition and Interpretation
3	Complex and Costly Clearance Procedures	Clearance procedures are complex, resource-intensive, and disproportionately burdensome for smaller countries.	Significant time and cost for regulatory compliance; burdens smaller MS with limited infrastructure.	2	Procedural and Operational Burdens
4	Narrow Focus on Radiological Aspects	Decisions are based solely on radiological safety without accounting for broader sustainability considerations.	Sustainability trade-offs (e.g., reuse vs. disposal) are not considered in regulatory decisions.	3	Scope and Integration of Regulatory Frameworks
5	Traceability Requirements Impede Recycling	Tracking requirements on cleared materials add administrative burden, discouraging recycling efforts.	Small quantities of cleared material are not reused due to traceability burdens and compliance risk.	2	Procedural and Operational Burdens
6	Lack of Correspondence between Nuclear and Conventional Waste Governance	Cleared materials face barriers entering conventional waste systems due to regulatory disconnect.	Recyclers may refuse safe materials; no mechanism for mutual recognition between frameworks.	3	Scope and Integration of Regulatory Frameworks
7	Lack of Support for Multicriteria and Life-Cycle Analysis	Lack of regulatory frameworks to enable life cycle or multicriteria-based decision-making.	Multicriteria assessment frameworks (e.g., LCA) are unsupported in regulation; planners lack tools.	3	Scope and Integration of Regulatory Frameworks
8	Inflexible Application of the Waste Management Hierarchy	Strict application of decontamination overrules the waste hierarchy, leading to inefficient disposal.	Regulators require maximum decontamination as a baseline for safety, alongside environmental and resource efficiency goals.	1	Legal Transposition and Interpretation
9	Outdated Technical Guidance (e.g., RP89 and RP122)	Existing EC guidance is outdated and does not reflect recent data or operational experience.	Operators and regulators rely on outdated dose coefficients and incomplete material categories.	4	Technical Standards and Support
10	Need for EC-Endorsed Tools and Guidance	Absence of standardized, EC-endorsed tools causes	Without shared clearance tools, operators develop ad hoc methods, causing	4	Technical Standards and Support

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

		inconsistencies and inefficiencies in clearance implementation.	inconsistency and delays.		
--	--	---	---------------------------	--	--

5.3.1 Analysis of issues:

Table 5 summarizes the regulatory issues analysed in the WP4 regulatory impact assessment, categorized according to their underlying nature — regulatory, strategic, or technical. Each issue has been classified using the decision-tree methodology outlined in Section 4.2.4 analysis, which distinguishes between legal frameworks, implementation challenges, planning gaps, and outdated technical standards. The summary highlights the essential rationale for each classification, drawing directly from the findings presented in the WP4 milestone. This structured overview is intended to provide a concise yet comprehensive reference point for understanding the nature of the barriers affecting circular economy implementation in nuclear waste management and decommissioning. The full analysis underlying these classifications is provided in Appendix B.

Table 5: **Classification of WP4 issues by type:** Categorization of issues affecting circular economy implementation by nature (regulatory, strategic, technical), with rationale.

Cluster	Issue No.	Issue Title	Classification	Summary of Rationale
1. Regulatory Frameworks	1	Inconsistent Transposition of EU Directive 2013/59	Regulatory	Different implementations across MS create inconsistencies in clearance practices, hindering cross-border recycling and reuse.
1. Regulatory Frameworks	2	Overly Stringent and Non-Risk-Based Approaches	Regulatory	Some national regulations exceed risk-informed standards, leading to unnecessary burdens and costs.
1. Regulatory Frameworks	3	Complex and Costly Clearance Procedures	Regulatory	Diverse clearance standards and documentation requirements across countries increase cost and complexity, limiting international recycling.
1. Regulatory Frameworks	5	Traceability Requirements Impede Recycling	Regulatory	Well-intended controls raise costs and create barriers to recycling; streamlined approaches could maintain safety and efficiency.
1. Regulatory Frameworks	6	Lack of correspondence between Nuclear and Conventional Waste Governance	Regulatory	Regulatory gaps between nuclear and conventional waste systems prevent integration of cleared materials into mainstream recycling.
2. Strategic & Planning Gaps	4	Narrow Focus on Radiological Aspects	Strategic	Lack of multicriteria analysis leads to decisions that overlook sustainability, environmental impact, and cost considerations.
2. Strategic & Planning Gaps	7	Lack of Support for Multicriteria and Life-Cycle Analysis	Strategic	Lack of guidance and tools limits the use of LCA and MCA for broader decision-making in decommissioning.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

2. Strategic & Planning Gaps	8	Inflexible Application of the Waste Management Hierarchy	Strategic	Rigid adherence to radiological safety limits compromises circular economy principles, i.e., reuse and recycling.
3. Technical Barriers	9	Outdated Technical Guidance (e.g., RP89 and RP122)	Technical	Old clearance guidance documents constrain sustainable material reuse and require updating to reflect current knowledge.
3. Technical Barriers	10	Need for EC-Endorsed Tools and Guidance	Technical	Lack of standardized tools leads to inefficiencies and inconsistent clearance practices across the EU.

5.3.2 Conclusion

The classification of issues presented in this section follows the application of the decision-tree methodology to the findings reported in the WP4 milestone. This method was used to assess whether the challenges raised in the context of decommissioning and circular economy implementation reflect regulatory obstacles, strategic planning gaps, technical limitations, or perceived barriers.

Several issues were identified as potentially regulatory in nature. These include inconsistencies in the application of clearance procedures, traceability requirements that may affect recycling, and the alignment between nuclear and conventional waste management frameworks. However, while these issues were provisionally classified as regulatory, further analysis is needed to determine whether their root causes lie within the regulatory framework itself, or whether they stem from implementation practices, interpretative differences, or other structural factors.

Other issues were classified as strategic or technical. In particular, the limited use of multicriteria analysis and life-cycle assessment in decision-making, as well as the reliance on outdated guidance documents, may point to gaps in planning tools and operational support rather than formal regulatory deficiencies.

Throughout the analysis, care has been taken to distinguish between barriers that are regulatory in origin and those that may be addressed through improved guidance, clarification, or coordination. It should also be noted that some challenges may reflect how regulations are applied in practice rather than shortcomings in the regulations themselves.

In summary, the findings suggest that while regulatory factors may play a role in shaping current practices, further investigation is required to clarify the extent to which

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

each issue is rooted in regulation, and to avoid drawing premature conclusions. A cautious and evidence-based approach is needed to ensure that any proposed solutions are appropriately targeted and proportionate.

5.4 WP5 Regulatory framework

The regulatory issues presented in this section are derived from findings in Milestone M22 – WP5 Regulatory Framework and Criteria Report, developed under the HARPERS project. Drawing on extensive input from stakeholder consultations, expert assessments, and regulatory reviews across EU MS, the report identifies 19 regulatory challenges linked to the implementation of advanced technologies in nuclear decommissioning and waste management.

These issues reflect challenges across areas such as regulatory clarity, the adaptation of frameworks to technological innovation, standardization, cybersecurity, and cross-border compatibility. Each presents a potential barrier to the safe, efficient, and harmonized use of innovative solutions such as digital twins, AI, robotics, and BIM in nuclear settings.

To support deeper analysis and more effective policy responses, the issues have been grouped into thematic clusters based on their underlying regulatory characteristics. These clusters distinguish between challenges related to:

1. Regulatory clarity, guidance, and frameworks.
2. Adaptation to technological innovation.
3. Technical standards and validation.
4. Awareness and understanding of regulatory requirements.
5. International harmonization and certification.
6. Regulator expertise and security concerns.

This clustering approach helps reveal systemic patterns and interdependencies across issues, enabling a more holistic understanding of where coordinated regulatory development or shared solutions may offer the most value. Table 6 provides a

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

summary of advanced technology-related issues identified in WP5, including reasons for regulatory relevance, implications, and proposed solutions.

Table 6: **Regulatory issues identified in WP5:** Summary of advanced technology-related issues identified in WP5, including reasons for regulatory relevance, implications, and proposed solutions.

Issue No.	WP5 Issue Name	Description	Examples/Impacts	Cluster No.	Cluster Name
1	Lack of Early Engagement During Technology Development	Developers face fragmented engagement across TRLs; regulators often join too late, causing rework.	Innovation sandboxes proposed for early multi-stakeholder dialogue.	1	Regulatory Clarity, Guidance, and Frameworks
2	Fragmented and Inconsistent Guidance Documentation	Documentation is hard to identify, varies across organisations and borders.	UK early engagement process for new nuclear build as model for decommissioning.	1	Regulatory Clarity, Guidance, and Frameworks
3	Overly General Guidance During Lifecycle Transitions	Ambiguity creates risk-aversion in early adoption of technologies.	Multi-organisational pilot initiatives to reduce uncertainty.	1	Regulatory Clarity, Guidance, and Frameworks
4	Regulations Not Enabling Risk-Proportional Measures	Some safety limits tighter than other public safety thresholds (e.g. food).	Call for standardised, flexible risk-based frameworks.	2	Adaptation to Technological Innovation
5	Rigid Waste Disposal Routes and Packaging Options	WACs are inherently site- and facility-specific, but differing national approaches to their development and interpretation may create uncertainty for technology developers and limit opportunities for cross-border innovation.	Differences in Waste Acceptance Criteria (WACs), which reflect repository-specific designs and safety cases, limit the ability to directly transfer innovative waste processing solutions across borders. Improved transparency and mutual understanding of WAC requirements could facilitate multinational operations, even though full harmonization is not feasible.	2	Adaptation to Technological Innovation
6	Lack of Awareness of Security-Related Requirements	Knowledge gaps cause delays, uncertainty, and higher costs.	Case studies and improved accessibility of requirements recommended.	3	Awareness and Understanding of Regulatory Requirements
7	Lack of Technical Standards for AI/Robotic Systems	Absence of shared standards increases complexity, safety risks.	Call for international technical standards for interoperability.	4	Technical Standards and Validation
8	Country-Specific Certification Mechanisms	Inconsistent national rules increase project costs and delay innovation.	Dialogue between regulators to harmonise best practices.	5	International Harmonization and Certification
9	Developers Unaware of Existing Regulatory Obligations	Legal uncertainty leads to business risks and project delays.	Easy-to-access regulation summaries and training recommended.	3	Awareness and Understanding of Regulatory Requirements

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

10	No Clear Framework for First-of-a-kind (FOAK) Technologies	Uncertainty discourages innovation and slows approval.	Exchange with countries having systematic FOAK regulation.	1	Regulatory Clarity, Guidance, and Frameworks
11	Difficult Validation of AI/Robotics in Harsh Environments	Hard to prove performance across extreme decommissioning scenarios.	AI-specific validation frameworks and simulation environments proposed.	4	Technical Standards and Validation
12	Lack of Digital Twin Regulation for Nuclear Decommissioning	Missing standards reduce effectiveness and safety.	Specific guidelines for digital twin development needed.	1	Regulatory Clarity, Guidance, and Frameworks
13	No Regulatory Framework for AI in Nuclear Decommissioning	Absence of guidelines slows adoption of safe AI tools.	Use sandboxes to explore safe implementation pathways.	1	Regulatory Clarity, Guidance, and Frameworks
14	No BIM Framework for Decommissioning	BIM use limited due to unclear regulations.	Interoperability and data management standards needed.	1	Regulatory Clarity, Guidance, and Frameworks
15	Unclear Adoption Path for BIM in Nuclear Context	General mandates don't address nuclear-specific use.	Specific guidance for nuclear BIM applications needed.	1	Regulatory Clarity, Guidance, and Frameworks
16	No Regulation for Using BIM/Digital Twins in Safety Reviews	Unrecognized potential to enhance safety assessments.	Define validation processes and data expectations.	1	Regulatory Clarity, Guidance, and Frameworks
17	Regulatory Development Lagging Behind Innovation	Outdated frameworks hinder new/innovative technology adoption.	Agile regulation systems needed to match pace of development.	2	Adaptation to Technological Innovation
18	Lack of Regulator Expertise in New Technologies	Knowledge gaps prevent effective evaluation and oversight.	Training programs for regulators on digital tools.	6	Regulator Expertise and Security Concerns
19	Cybersecurity Classification Ambiguity	Unclear if cyber concerns are technical or regulatory.	Clear cybersecurity regulation approach recommended.	6	Regulator Expertise and Security Concerns

5.4.1 Analysis of issues:

The table below summarizes the regulatory challenges identified and assessed in WP5, grouped according to their thematic clusters and classified as regulatory, strategic, perceived, or technical in nature. MS Each issue has been classified using the decision-tree methodology outlined in Section 4.2.4. The classification reflects the root nature of each issue, i.e., whether perceived, strategic, technical or regulatory. The rationale for each entry is drawn from the WP5 findings, providing a clear overview of the key barriers that affect the safe and effective integration of advanced technologies in nuclear waste management and decommissioning. Further detail and supporting analysis for each issue can be found in Appendix C.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

Table 7: **Classification of WP5 issues by type:** Categorization of WP5 issues as regulatory, strategic, technical, or perceived, with brief justification for each.

Cluster	Issue No.	Issue Title	Classification	Summary of Rationale
1. Regulatory Clarity, Guidance, and Frameworks	1	Lack of Early Engagement During Technology Development	Strategic	Late engagement with regulator leads to unanticipated obligations; early engagement can improve planning and reduce risk.
1. Regulatory Clarity, Guidance, and Frameworks	2	Fragmented and Inconsistent Guidance Documentation	Strategic	Inconsistent and hard-to-find guidance slows innovation and creates uncertainty across jurisdictions.
1. Regulatory Clarity, Guidance, and Frameworks	3	Overly General Guidance During Lifecycle Transitions	Strategic	Broad, non-specific guidance deters trial of new technologies and increases perceived risk.
2. Adaptation to Technological Innovation	4	Regulations Not Enabling Risk-Proportional Measures	Perceived	Disproportionate limits (e.g., on radiation) create unnecessary burdens; flexible, risk-informed rules are needed.
2. Adaptation to Technological Innovation	5	Rigid Waste Disposal Routes and Packaging Options	Strategic	Waste Acceptance Criteria (WACs) differ between countries based on repository design and specific safety cases; while harmonization is not straightforward, these differences may limit cross-border adoption of new waste processing solutions.
3. Awareness and Understanding of Regulatory Requirements	6	Lack of Awareness of Security-Related Requirements	Perceived	Developers may overlook key requirements due to limited awareness, increasing delays and costs.
4. Technical Standards and Validation	7	Lack of Technical Standards for AI/Robotic Systems	Strategic	Absence of common standards increases safety risks and slows certification and interoperability.
5. International Harmonization and Certification	8	Country-Specific Certification Mechanisms	Strategic	Regulatory differences between countries raise costs and block international collaboration.
3. Awareness and Understanding of Regulatory Requirements	9	Developers Unaware of Existing Regulatory Obligations	Perceived	Developers not traditionally involved in the nuclear sector may face uncertainty about regulatory obligations, which has been associated with compliance gaps, delays, and rework in some cases.
1. Regulatory Clarity, Guidance, and Frameworks	10	No Clear Framework for FOAK Technologies	Strategic	Lack of clear approval pathways deters innovation and slows technology deployment.
4. Technical Standards and Validation	11	Difficult Validation of AI/Robotics in Harsh Environments	Technical	AI/robotics face validation difficulties under nuclear conditions; tailored Verification & Validation processes are required.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

1. Regulatory Clarity, Guidance, and Frameworks	12	Lack of Digital Twin Regulation for Nuclear Decommissioning	Regulatory	Digital twins lack regulatory recognition and guidance, causing inconsistent integration into safety processes.
1. Regulatory Clarity, Guidance, and Frameworks	13	No Regulatory Framework for AI in Nuclear Decommissioning	Regulatory	Without clear AI regulations, adoption is delayed, and oversight remains unclear.
1. Regulatory Clarity, Guidance, and Frameworks	14	No regulatory or standardized technical framework exists for the use of Building Information Modelling (BIM) in nuclear decommissioning, creating uncertainty about data requirements, validation, and regulatory acceptance.	Strategic	BIM use in nuclear is hindered by unclear guidance and lack of interoperability standards.
1. Regulatory Clarity, Guidance, and Frameworks	15	Even where BIM is being piloted for decommissioning, there is no clearly defined adoption path detailing how BIM-based models and data should be validated, submitted, and accepted within regulatory processes. This creates uncertainty for implementers.	Strategic	General mandates don't clarify nuclear-specific applications, causing hesitation and inconsistent use.
1. Regulatory Clarity, Guidance, and Frameworks	16	No Regulation for Using BIM/Digital Twins in Safety Reviews	Strategic	Lack of clear rules complicates use of advanced tools in safety cases despite their potential benefits.
2. Adaptation to Technological Innovation	17	Regulatory Development Lagging Behind Innovation	Regulatory	Technology is advancing faster than regulations, creating delays and discouraging innovation.
6. Regulator Expertise and Security Concerns	18	Lack of Regulator Expertise in New Technologies	Strategic	Gaps in regulator understanding lead to inconsistent oversight and slow response to innovations.
6. Regulator Expertise and Security Concerns	19	Cybersecurity Classification Ambiguity	Regulatory	Current cybersecurity frameworks do not always clearly classify whether digital systems fall under nuclear safety, nuclear security, or general IT regulations, potentially leading to inconsistent requirements across different types of systems..

5.4.2 Conclusion

The classification of issues presented in this section is based on the decision-tree methodology outlined in Section 4.2.4., which applies a structured methodology to distinguish between regulatory, strategic, technical, and perceived barriers affecting the deployment of advanced technologies in nuclear waste management and decommissioning. In this context, a regulatory issue is understood as a challenge that arises from the absence, insufficiency, or misalignment of formal legal frameworks,

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

regulatory requirements, or compliance mechanisms. This includes situations where existing regulations do not account for technological developments, or where a lack of regulatory clarity may impede innovation and implementation.

The majority of the issues reviewed under WP5 were found to reflect a combination of planning challenges, awareness gaps, or technical barriers. Strategic issues were particularly associated with unclear guidance during lifecycle transitions, limited early engagement between regulators and developers, and rigid frameworks that hinder risk-proportional approaches or cross-border coordination. Several technical and perceived issues stemmed from a lack of standards or understanding, such as difficulties in validating AI/robotics, or limited awareness of security-related requirements. In many cases, the root causes appear to lie in interpretation, fragmented practices, or outdated procedures, rather than in the legal texts themselves.

However, four issues were classified as regulatory in nature. These include the lack of standardised regulations for digital twin implementation, the absence of an established regulatory framework for AI applications in the nuclear sector, the slow pace of regulatory development in comparison to technological advancement, and the unclear classification of cybersecurity concerns as regulatory or technical matters. These issues are notable in that they reflect fundamental gaps in the regulatory environment, where emerging technologies are either not addressed at all or are inconsistently treated across jurisdictions. The lack of formal recognition and guidance not only introduces uncertainty for developers and operators but also places regulators in a reactive position, often without the tools or criteria needed to provide timely and consistent oversight.

In conclusion, the WP5 findings highlight that while many challenges can be addressed through better coordination, improved guidance, or updated technical standards, there remains a critical need to strengthen the regulatory foundations for new technologies. This will require deliberate efforts to modernise regulatory frameworks, clarify responsibilities, and build regulatory capacity in emerging domains. Addressing the four regulatory issues identified here will be essential to ensuring that innovation in nuclear decommissioning can proceed safely, efficiently, and in alignment with broader policy goals.

6 Conclusions and Recommendations

6.1 Introduction

This chapter brings together the key findings from the regulatory analyses conducted under Work Packages 3, 4, and 5 of the EURATOM HARPERS project, and presents a set of recommendations based on the evidence and classifications developed in Work Package 6. The conclusions reflect a structured assessment of regulatory, strategic, technical, and perceived issues across three thematic areas: cross-border radioactive waste management, circular economy in nuclear waste management and decommissioning, and the adoption of advanced technologies.

Each subsection summarises the main insights from the relevant work package, outlining where existing regulatory frameworks are functioning effectively, where improvements could enhance consistency and coordination, and where further guidance, tools, or collaboration are needed. The recommendations provided are intended to support policymakers, regulators, and stakeholders in addressing the most pressing challenges identified in the analysis, while enabling more aligned and forward-thinking regulatory approaches across the EU.

More detailed analysis, supporting evidence, and rationale for the issue classifications referenced in this chapter can be found in Appendices A, B, and C, which correspond to WP6 analysis of the outputs of WP3, WP4, and WP5 respectively.

6.2 WP3 – Cross border services / facilities

WP3 assessed barriers to the effective management of problematic and hazardous radioactive waste across the EU, with a particular focus on cross-border cooperation. Using a structured decision-tree approach, nine issues (preliminarily identified by WP3 as being regulatory in nature) were classified based on whether they are regulatory, strategic, technical, or perceived challenges. The classification was informed by stakeholder responses, national case studies, and existing legal frameworks.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

A key finding is that few of these obstacles to cross-border RAW management were considered to be regulatory. Rather than pointing to gaps in legal provisions, most challenges relate to differences in interpretation, prioritisation, or understanding. In many cases, existing frameworks at national and EU levels already provide a workable basis for cooperation. Successful examples, such as the Orano La Hague facility and Cyclife operations, show that cross-border treatment and return can proceed under current regulations when coordination is strong, and stakeholder roles are clearly defined.

Only three of the issues were ultimately classified as regulatory. These relate to the lack of an aligned definition for problematic waste, diverging legal interpretations of hazardous RAW, and differences in national waste classification systems. Each reflects the absence of alignment at a higher level rather than deficiencies in legal structure. Addressing these issues would support better coordination, comparability, and shared infrastructure use across MS.

The remaining issues fall into perceived, strategic, or technical categories. The lack of aligned Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC) expectations and legal barriers to cross-border movement are often perceived rather than actual regulatory problems. In both cases, practical examples show that solutions exist within current frameworks. Strategic issues, such as inconsistent national prioritisation and societal resistance to facility development, point to planning and coordination gaps rather than regulatory matters. The only technical issue identified—the absence of treatment infrastructure for hazardous RAW—highlights a need for investment, particularly in shared European solutions.

Based on these findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. **Enhance strategic alignment across MS**

There may be value in national programmes placing greater emphasis on harmonising definitions (e.g., for problematic waste) and aligning planning priorities, as this could help reduce uncertainty for stakeholders and support more consistent cross-border cooperation.

2. Clarify and communicate Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC) needs and expectations

Where WAC are still under development, it may be helpful for clear guidance or case examples to be provided at the EU level to clarify expectations. This could help address perceived barriers and build confidence in the return of waste following treatment abroad.

3. Promote best practices in cross-border cooperation

Sharing successful examples of international collaboration—particularly those involving effective stakeholder engagement, regulator coordination, and joint planning—may help other Member States overcome perceived or practical barriers.

4. Develop a common definition of problematic waste at the EU or international level

A unified definition could support improved inventory development, waste classification, and alignment of treatment strategies

5. Align treatment of hazardous RAW

Clarifying whether hazardous RAW is subject to parallel or integrated regulation across Member States could help reduce complexity and support smoother cross-border handling and disposal.

6. Support the joint development of treatment infrastructure

In cases where national solutions are not feasible, Member States may wish to explore cooperative approaches to facility development for hazardous RAW.

7. Improve coordination and communication among authorities

There may be benefit in further explaining and coordinating administrative and legal pathways for import/export, to help avoid confusion and delays, even where enabling legislation is already in place.

In conclusion, the WP3-related findings suggest that while some regulatory improvements — particularly in the areas of definitions and classification — may be beneficial, the main challenges to cross-border RAW management appear to be strategic and organisational. Supporting a more harmonised and effective waste management framework across the EU may therefore depend on continued improvements in planning, guidance, and cooperation.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

6.3 WP4 – Circular Economy

The WP4 analysis reviewed ten challenges affecting the integration of circular economy principles into nuclear waste management and decommissioning, with a particular focus on material clearance, reuse, and the interface between nuclear and conventional waste systems. These challenges were assessed through a structured classification process, drawing on stakeholder input and technical review, to determine whether the issues relate primarily to regulatory frameworks, strategic planning gaps, or technical limitations.

A number of the issues identified in this analysis appear to stem from how existing regulations are implemented, interpreted, or aligned across Member States. While formal regulatory structures are in place, differences in national approaches to clearance, risk assessment, and classification may create complexity for operators and could hinder efforts to promote the reuse and recycling of materials. For example, variation in the transposition of EU Directive 2013/59/Euratom and differences in the application of clearance thresholds may contribute to inconsistent outcomes across jurisdictions. These inconsistencies do not indicate deficiencies in the regulations themselves, but rather reflect differences in interpretation, procedural design, or supporting guidance.

Several challenges were also classified as strategic. These include the limited application of multicriteria and life-cycle analysis in clearance decision-making, and the absence of practical mechanisms to integrate environmental and resource considerations alongside radiological protection. These gaps do not point to legal shortcomings but suggest that existing frameworks could better support broader policy objectives through improved planning tools and clearer regulatory expectations.

Two issues were classified as being technical in nature. These relate to the continued use of outdated guidance documents and the absence of standardised tools to support clearance calculations and regulatory submissions. While these limitations are not regulatory barriers in a strict sense, they can contribute to delays, duplication of effort, and reduced consistency in implementation.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

Overall, the WP4-related findings indicate that many of the challenges in applying circular economy principles to nuclear waste management and decommissioning may be linked to the complexity of regulatory frameworks and variations in their interpretation or implementation, rather than to gaps in regulation itself. Enhancing the clarity, consistency, and practical application of existing frameworks — alongside improved technical support — could help facilitate safer, more efficient, and environmentally responsible reuse of materials.

Based on this analysis, the following recommendations are proposed:

- 1. Improve regulatory alignment across MS**

There may be value in supporting efforts to achieve more consistent implementation of EU directives and clearance frameworks, particularly by providing clearer interpretation and guidance on the risk-based application of thresholds.

- 2. Support harmonised clearance procedures and mutual understanding**

Exploring shared approaches to clearance thresholds, measurement protocols, and documentation could help facilitate smoother cooperation and reduce administrative burden, particularly in cross-border contexts.

- 3. Update technical guidance documents**

Consider revising and updating existing EC Radiation Protection Series documents (e.g., RP-89, RP-122) to reflect current scientific understanding and operational experience, including updated dose coefficients and radionuclide data.

- 4. Develop common tools for clearance calculations**

Encourage the development of standardised, EC-endorsed tools for clearance assessments to support regulatory consistency and reduce reliance on bespoke national systems.

- 5. Encourage broader decision-making frameworks**

Promote the integration of multicriteria analysis and life-cycle assessment into clearance and decommissioning planning, where appropriate, to support balanced and transparent decision-making.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

6. **Clarify the interface between nuclear and conventional waste systems**

Explore mechanisms to improve coordination and mutual recognition between regulatory frameworks, to ensure that cleared materials can be safely and effectively reused in conventional sectors.

7. **Review administrative requirements for traceability**

Consider where risk-informed approaches could be applied to streamline traceability requirements for cleared materials, particularly where levels of residual radioactivity are well below safety thresholds.

In conclusion, the analysis of WP4-related outcomes highlights that many of the practical challenges to circular economy implementation in nuclear waste management and decommissioning relate to differences in regulatory interpretation, procedural design, and supporting tools. Addressing these areas through clearer guidance, better coordination, and technical updates would help align regulatory practice with broader policy objectives, without compromising safety or public confidence.

6.4 WP5 – Advanced Technologies

WP5 examined the regulatory challenges associated with the use of advanced technologies in nuclear decommissioning, including digital twins, artificial intelligence, robotics, and building information modelling. Identified issues were classified based on their underlying nature—whether regulatory, strategic, technical, or perceived—and assessed using a structured framework informed by stakeholder input and a review of current regulatory practices.

The findings show that while many of the challenges relate to planning, coordination, or technical matters, four issues were identified as being regulatory in nature. These include the absence of specific regulation for digital twin applications, the lack of a regulatory framework for AI in waste management and decommissioning, the slow pace of regulatory development compared to technological innovation, and the unclear classification of cybersecurity as either a technical or regulatory matter. These issues potentially highlight gaps in existing regulatory systems that may hinder the effective and consistent use of new technologies.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

Other issues reflect broader implementation challenges. These include inconsistent guidance, limited awareness of regulatory requirements, difficulties with validation in demanding environments, and variations in national certification processes. Although these are not strictly regulatory problems, they affect how regulations are applied and understood in practice.

In response to these findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1 Develop clear guidance for new technologies

Develop and publish practical regulatory guidance on how digital twins, AI, and BIM can be used in decommissioning. This should include expectations for validation, integration into safety cases, and documentation requirements.

2 Establish formal regulatory frameworks for AI

Develop a regulatory framework to support the use of AI in nuclear decommissioning, including defined approval processes and performance criteria. Pilot projects and regulatory sandboxes can be used to support this work.

3 Modernise regulatory systems

Adopt more flexible processes within regulatory systems to keep pace with innovation. This may include interim guidance, use of pilot evaluations, and regular reviews to update regulatory positions as technologies evolve.

4 Clarify cybersecurity responsibilities

Define how cybersecurity risks are classified and regulated in the context of decommissioning technologies. This should involve all relevant authorities and clearly distinguish between technical controls and regulatory oversight.

5 Encourage early and structured engagement

Set up processes to allow early dialogue between developers and regulators, particularly during technology development. This could include formalised pre-licensing discussions or innovation review panels.

6 Improve consistency across jurisdictions

Where possible, align regulatory approaches to certification, risk assessment, and validation. Sharing regulatory experience and lessons learned will help reduce duplication and improve confidence in new approaches.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

7 Strengthen regulator expertise

Build internal capacity within regulatory bodies in areas such as AI, robotics, and cybersecurity. This may involve training, recruitment of technical specialists, and collaboration with research organisations.

8 Support the development of technical standards

Develop or adapt relevant standards for the validation and use of digital and automated systems for the decommissioning context. This would benefit from industry and regulators working jointly on this effort.

9 Improve access to regulatory information

Ensure that regulatory expectations are communicated clearly and accessibly, particularly to organisations that are new to the nuclear sector. This includes the publication of plain-language summaries and supporting material.

In conclusion, the analysis highlights the need to address specific gaps in regulatory frameworks, while also improving implementation, guidance, and technical consistency. By acting on the recommendations set out above, it will be possible to support the safe and effective use of advanced technologies in nuclear decommissioning, and to ensure that regulation remains an enabler of innovation rather than a barrier to progress.

6.5 Conclusion

The analyses of issues identified in WP3, WP4, and WP5 have shown that while regulatory barriers do exist in some areas, many of the challenges facing cross-border radioactive waste management, circular economy implementation, and the adoption of advanced technologies stem from differences in interpretation, planning, and technical capacity rather than from gaps in legislation itself. By classifying issues as regulatory, strategic, technical, or perceived, WP6 has clarified where targeted improvements can be made.

The recommendations presented in this chapter reflect both topic-specific insights and broader, cross-cutting needs. To support a more consistent and forward-looking approach across the EU, a set of six priority actions has been identified. These recommendations aim to enhance clarity, coordination, and capacity within the regulatory landscape — ensuring that current frameworks not only safeguard safety

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

and compliance, but also enable innovation, efficiency, and sustainable practices in nuclear decommissioning and waste management. The table below summarises these key areas for action, as a basis for further discussion and policy development.

Table 8: **Key policy recommendations across work packages:** Summary of priority actions to address cross-cutting regulatory, strategic, and technical challenges from WP3, WP4, and WP5.

Key Recommendation	Issue Addressed	Relevant Work Packages
Align definitions and classification standards	Inconsistent definitions across MS of problematic waste, hazardous RAW, and clearance thresholds	WP3, WP4
Clarify and update EU-level regulatory guidance and tools	Outdated technical documents, inconsistent implementation	WP3, WP4, WP5
Develop regulatory frameworks for advanced technologies	Lack of regulation for AI, BIM, digital twins, and cybersecurity responsibilities	WP5
Improve strategic alignment and planning coordination	Divergent national priorities, limited coordination on infrastructure and circular economy planning	WP3, WP4
Strengthen regulatory capacity and stakeholder engagement	Gaps in regulator expertise, limited early dialogue, public and stakeholder misunderstanding	WP3, WP5
Promote mutual recognition and cross-border cooperation	National certification differences, clearance procedure mismatches, legal uncertainty in transport	WP3, WP4, WP5

7 References

- [1] European Atomic Energy Community, “Treaty Establishing the European Atomic Energy Community,” 1957.
- [2] French Authority for Nuclear Safety (ASN), “The European Union.” [Online]. Available: <https://www.french-nuclear-safety.fr/international-relations/multilateral-relations-in-europe2/the-european-union>
- [3] “Council Directive 2013/59/Euratom of 5 December 2013 laying down basic safety standards for protection against the dangers arising from exposure to ionising radiation,” 2014.
- [4] “Council Directive 2014/87/Euratom of 8 July 2014 amending Directive 2009/71/Euratom establishing a Community framework for the nuclear safety of nuclear installations,” 2014.
- [5] “Council Directive 2011/70/Euratom of 19 July 2011 establishing a Community framework for the responsible and safe management of spent fuel and radioactive waste,” 2011.
- [6] European Court of Auditors, “Special Report 03/2020: The Commission contributes to nuclear safety in the EU, but updates required,” 2020. [Online]. Available: https://www.eca.europa.eu/lists/ecadocuments/sr20_03/sr_nuclear-safety_en.pdf
- [7] Health and Safety Executive (HSE), “Consultation on the Implementation of Directive 2013/59/EURATOM: Basic Safety Standards for Protection Against the Dangers Arising from Exposure to Ionising Radiation – Occupational Health and Safety,” Feb. 2017, *Redgrave Court, Merton Rd, Bootle, Merseyside, L20 7HS*.
- [8] Western European Nuclear Regulators Association (WENRA), “Preliminary Status of the Implementation of the 2020 Safety

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

Reference Levels in National Regulatory Frameworks as of 1 January 2024,” Apr. 2024. [Online]. Available: https://www.wenra.eu/sites/default/files/publications/Status_of_Implementation_of_2020SRLs_in_NationalRegulatoryFrameworks_as_of_1January2024.pdf

- [9] Western European Nuclear Regulators Association (WENRA), “Working Group on Waste and Decommissioning (WGWD).” Accessed: Apr. 29, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.wenra.eu/working-group-waste-and-decommissioning-wgwd>
- [10] Western European Nuclear Regulators Association (WENRA), “WENRA Brochure.” Accessed: Apr. 29, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://www.wenra.eu/sites/default/files/WENRA_Brochure.pdf
- [11] Nuclear Energy Agency, *Nuclear Site Remediation and Restoration during Decommissioning of Nuclear Installations*. Paris: OECD Publishing, 2014. [Online]. Available: https://www.oecd-neo.org/jcms/pl_14900/nuclear-site-remediation-and-restoration-during-decommissioning-of-nuclear-installations?details=true
- [12] “Sixth Situation Report on Radioactive Waste and Spent Fuel Management in the European Union,” Brussels, Sep. 2008. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:52008SC2416>
- [13] M. G. Faure and K. Kindji, *Cross-border nuclear safety, liability and cooperation in the European Union*. Edited by M. G. Faure and K. Kindji (they edited and contributed), 2019.
- [14] “Council Directive 2006/117/Euratom of 20 November 2006 on the supervision and control of shipments of radioactive waste and spent fuel,” 2006.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

- [15] IAEA., *Status and trends in spent fuel and radioactive waste management*. IAEA, 2018.
- [16] Fortum, “Nuclear Waste Management,” 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://www.fortum.com/media/2016/05/nuclear-waste-management>
- [17] OECD Nuclear Energy Agency (NEA), *Nuclear Legislation in OECD Countries: Sweden*. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2003. [Online]. Available: <https://www.oecd-nea.org/upload/docs/application/pdf/2020-11/sweden.pdf>
- [18] Kingdom of the Netherlands and United Kingdom, “Agreement between the Kingdom of the Netherlands and the United Kingdom concerning the Delimitation of the Continental Shelf under the North Sea,” 1965. [Online]. Available: <https://international.vlex.com/vid/agreement-between-the-kingdom-851217648>
- [19] World Nuclear Association, “International Nuclear Waste Disposal Concepts,” Apr. 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://world-nuclear.org/information-library/nuclear-fuel-cycle/nuclear-waste/international-nuclear-waste-disposal-concepts>
- [20] A. Matting, “Regulatory Control of the German Radioactive Waste Management System,” *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, vol. 176, no. 1–2, pp. 141–144, 1997, doi: 10.1016/S0029-5493(96)01341-6.
- [21] IDOM, “Radioactive Waste Classification Study,” May 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.idom.com/en/new/radioactive-waste-classification-study/>
- [22] C. McCombie and N. Chapman, “Sharing geological repositories,” *Nuclear Engineering International*, [Online]. Available: <https://www.neimagazine.com/analysis/sharing-geological-repositories/>

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

- [23] nucleareurope, “Nuclear Waste.” [Online]. Available: <https://www.nucleareurope.eu/project/nuclear-waste/>
- [24] A. Wareing, “Milestone 2.4 Strategic Research Agenda,” May 2023. [Online]. Available: https://predis-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/PREDIS-SRA_Milestone-Report-2.4_May-2023.pdf
- [25] DKE, “The Harmonized Standards System (HAS),” Aug. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.dke.de/en/standards-and-specifications/policy-law-strategy/news/harmonized-standards-system>
- [26] International Atomic Energy Agency, *Application of the Concept of Clearance*. Vienna: International Atomic Energy Agency, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iaea.org/publications/15291/application-of-the-concept-of-clearance>
- [27] B. Ooms *et al.*, “Recycling and Reuse of Materials Arising from the Decommissioning of Nuclear Facilities. A Report by the NEA Co-operative Program on Decommissioning,” 2017.
- [28] A. Larsson, M. Lindberg, G. Krause, R. Matsson, and A. Stenmark, “Melting of Contaminated Metals for Clearance and Recycling – 30+ Years of Practical Experience,” in *International Conference on Radioactive Waste Management: Solutions for a Sustainable Future*, 2021, p. 86. [Online]. Available: <https://inis.iaea.org/records/z09qe-bma16>
- [29] European Union, “Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on Waste and Repealing Certain Directives,” 2008. [Online]. Available: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/waste-and-recycling/waste-framework-directive_en

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

- [30] B. Ooms *et al.*, “Recycling and Reuse of Materials Arising from the Decommissioning of Nuclear Facilities. A Report by the NEA Co-operative Program on Decommissioning,” 2017.
- [31] Sellafield Ltd, “Sellafield robots leading an evolution in nuclear decommissioning,” Nov. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/sellafield-robots-leading-an-evolution-in-nuclear-decommissioning>
- [32] Framatome, “Framatome helps advance use of robotics in nuclear D&D,” May 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ans.org/news/article-2909/framatome-helps-advance-use-of-robotics-in-nuclear-dd/>
- [33] H. Wegstein and I. Jamieson, “Brennilis - First Deployment of Industrial Robots for the Dismantling of a French Nuclear Power Plant,” in *ECED 2013: Eastern and Central Europe Decommissioning. International Conference on Decommissioning of Nuclear Facilities. Conference Guide and Book of Abstracts*, 2013, p. 36. [Online]. Available: <https://inis.iaea.org/records/2pvn1-vra40>
- [34] T. Kumazawa, T. Suzuki, Y. Takahashi, and Y. Nakahara, “Comprehensive support for nuclear decommissioning based on 3D simulation and virtual reality technologies,” *J Nucl Sci Technol*, vol. 51, no. 7–8, pp. 968–975, 2014, doi: 10.1080/00223131.2014.951704.
- [35] J. Donovan, “Robots, AI and 3D Models: How High-tech Breakthroughs Help Nuclear Decommissioning,” *IAEA Bulletin*, 2023, [Online]. Available: <https://www.iaea.org/bulletin/robots-ai-and-3d-models-how-high-tech-breakthroughs-help-nuclear-decommissioning>
- [36] S. Menon, E. Lazo, J. Claes, and C. Pescatore, “The NEA Co-Operative Programme on Decommissioning: Fifteen Years of

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

Experience,” in *International Conference on Radioactive Waste Management and Environmental Remediation*, American Society of Mechanical Engineers, 2001, pp. 51–55. doi: 10.1115/ICEM2001-1166.

- [37] International Atomic Energy Agency, “Strengthening the Agency’s Activities related to Nuclear Science and Technology,” 2024. Accessed: Apr. 29, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iaea.org/sites/default/files/gc/gc68-10.pdf>
- [38] M. Di Giovanni *et al.*, “Supporting the development of digital twins in nuclear waste monitoring systems,” *Procedia Comput Sci*, vol. 225, pp. 3133–3142, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2023.10.307.
- [39] M. Garcia, T. Beattie, and S. Schumacher, “EURAD – the European Joint Programme for research on radioactive waste management between EU member states national programmes,” *EPJ Nuclear Sciences & Technologies*, vol. 6, p. 21, 2020, doi: 10.1051/epjn/2019044.
- [40] European Commission, “Horizon Europe Cluster 4: Digital, Industry, and Space,” 2021. [Online]. Available: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/cluster-4-digital-industry-and-space_en
- [41] F. E. Schneider, “ENRICH will test robots in real world radiological and nuclear scenarios,” *Robohub*, Feb. 2017, [Online]. Available: <https://robohub.org/enrich-will-test-robots-in-real-world-radiological-and-nuclear-scenarios/>
- [42] Diakont, “Robotic BWR Torus Inspection,” 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://diakont.com/nuclear-services/robotic-bwr-torus-inspection/>
- [43] International Atomic Energy Agency, “NEW CRP: Deployment of Innovative Digital Technologies for Efficient Decommissioning of

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

Nuclear Facilities (DEDICATE)," Sep. 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iaea.org/newscenter/news/new-crp-deployment-of-innovative-digital-technologies-for-efficient-decommissioning-of-nuclear-facilities-dedicate>

- [44] Assystem, "Realisation of a BIM Model for the Dismantling of a Nuclear Reactor," 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.assystem.com/en/references/realisation-of-a-bim-model-for-the-dismantling-of-a-nuclear-reactor/>
- [45] International Organization for Standardization, "ISO 10218-2:2025 – Robotics — Safety Requirements — Part 2: Robot Systems and Integration," Feb. 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/73934.html>
- [46] V. Yadav *et al.*, "Regulatory Considerations for Nuclear Energy Applications of Digital Twin Technologies," Aug. 2022. doi: 10.2172/1984814.
- [47] M. D. Muhlheim, P. Ramuhalli, A. Huning, A. Guler Yigitoglu, R. T. Wood, and A. Saxena, "Status Report on Regulatory Criteria Applicable to the Use of Digital Twins," Jun. 2022. doi: 10.2172/1883838.
- [48] R. Stewart, A. Shields, S. Bays, C. Ritter, G. Reyes, and M. Schanfein, "Utilizing Digital Twins for Nuclear Safeguards and Security," in *Proceedings of the INMM & ESARDA 2023 Joint Annual Meeting*, Vienna, Austria, 2023. [Online]. Available: https://resources.inmm.org/sites/default/files/2023-07/finalpaper_210_0513113916.pdf
- [49] Nuclear Energy Agency, "Status, Barriers and Cost-Benefits of Robotic and Remote Systems Applications in Nuclear Decommissioning and Radioactive Waste Management," 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.oecd->

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

nea.org/jcms/pl_77051/status-barriers-and-cost-benefits-of-robotic-and-remote-systems-applications-in-nuclear-decommissioning-and-radioactive-waste-management

- [50] European Atomic Energy Community, “Report on the Implementation of the Obligations under the Joint Convention on the Safety of Spent Fuel Management and on the Safety of Radioactive Waste Management,” May 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iaea.org/sites/default/files/euratom-7rm.pdf>
- [51] International Commission on Radiological Protection, “The 2007 Recommendations of the International Commission on Radiological Protection,” *Ann ICRP*, vol. 37, no. 2–4, pp. 1–332, 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.icrp.2007.10.003.
- [52] Autoridad Regulatoria Nuclear (ARN) and International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), “Radioactivity in Goods Supplied for Public Consumption or Use: Towards an Internationally Harmonized Regulatory Framework,” Jan. 2019. [Online]. Available: https://www.iaea.org/sites/default/files/19/02/iaea-arn_document_on_consumer_goods.pdf
- [53] S. O. Hansson, “ALARA: What is Reasonably Achievable?,” in *Radioactivity in the Environment*, vol. 19, Elsevier, 2013, pp. 143–155. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-08-045015-5.00009-5.
- [54] L. Abrahamsen-Mills, A. Wareing, L. Fowler, R. Jarvis, S. Norris, and A. Banford, “Development of a multi criteria decision analysis framework for the assessment of integrated waste management options for irradiated graphite,” *Nuclear Engineering and Technology*, vol. 53, no. 4, pp. 1224–1235, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.net.2020.10.008.
- [55] J. Kirk, R. Clayton, A. Banford, and L. Stamford, “Environmental impacts of decommissioning a nuclear power plant: A life cycle

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

assessment of a Magnox site,” *Environ Impact Assess Rev*, vol. 113, p. 107880, 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.eiar.2025.107880.

- [56] U.S. Nuclear Regulatory Commission, “Information Notice No. 86-25: Traceability and Material Control of Material and Equipment, Particularly Fasteners,” Apr. 1986.
- [57] European Commission, “New clearance procedure to cut radioactive waste production from decommissioning activities at the JRC Ispra site,” Jan. 2025.
- [58] “Analysis of the Factors Influencing the Selection of Strategies for Decommissioning of Nuclear Installations,” European Commission, 2009. [Online]. Available: <https://igdtp.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/CND-D8.1-Final.pdf>
- [59] Y. A. Suh, C. Hornibrook, and M. S. Yim, “Decisions on Nuclear Decommissioning Strategies: Historical Review,” *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, vol. 106, pp. 34–43, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.pnucene.2018.02.015.
- [60] Nuclear Decommissioning Authority, “Case Studies: Site Decommissioning and Remediation Strategic Theme,” Oct. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/nuclear-decommissioning-authority-annual-report-and-accounts-2022-to-2023/case-studies-site-decommissioning-and-remediation-strategic-theme>
- [61] U.S. Nuclear Regulatory Commission, “Digital Twins,” Dec. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nrc.gov/reactors/power/digital-twins.html>
- [62] Office for Nuclear Regulation, “Office for Nuclear Regulation Corporate Plan 2024 to 2025,” May 2024. [Online]. Available:

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/office-for-nuclear-regulation-corporate-plan-2024-to-2025>

- [63] T. Higgins, K. W. Irvin, A. L. Flyer, and N. E. Noëlliste, “U.S. Nuclear Regulatory Commission Proposes New Licensing Framework for Advanced Reactors,” *Environmental and Energy Brief*, Nov. 2024, [Online]. Available: <https://environmentalenergybrief.sidley.com/2024/11/08/u-s-nuclear-regulatory-commission-proposes-new-licensing-framework-for-advanced-reactors/>
- [64] Nuclear Energy Agency, “Regulating AI Use During SMR Deployment,” Feb. 2025. [Online]. Available: https://www.oecd-nea.org/jcms/pl_101324/regulating-ai-use-during-smr-deployment
- [65] U.S. Nuclear Regulatory Commission, “Risk-Informed Decision-Making for Nuclear Material and Waste Applications,” Feb. 2008. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nrc.gov/docs/ml0807/ml080720238.pdf>
- [66] Nuclear Innovation Alliance, “Due Diligence for Advanced Nuclear Technology Companies: A Guide for Potential Investors,” Oct. 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nuclearinnovationalliance.org/due-diligence-advanced-nuclear-technology-companies-guide-potential-investor>
- [67] Nuclear Energy Agency, “Addressing the Challenges in the Nuclear Supply Chain to Ensure Safe and Reliable Nuclear Operations,” Mar. 2024. [Online]. Available: https://www.oecd-nea.org/jcms/pl_91580/addressing-the-challenges-in-the-nuclear-supply-chain-to-ensure-safe-and-reliable-nuclear-operations
- [68] R. Smith, E. Cucco, and C. Fairbairn, “Robotic Development for the Nuclear Environment: Challenges and Strategy,” *Robotics*, vol. 9, no. 4, p. 94, 2020, doi: 10.3390/robotics9040094.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

- [69] M. Krichen, “A survey on formal verification and validation techniques for internet of things,” *Applied Sciences*, vol. 13, no. 14, p. 8122, 2023.
- [70] Nuclear Energy Agency (NEA), “Status, Barriers and Cost-Benefits of Robotic and Remote Systems Applications in Nuclear Decommissioning and Radioactive Waste Management,” Paris, 2023. [Online]. Available: https://www.oecd-nea.org/upload/docs/application/pdf/2023-01/4b_-_nea_rwm_r_2022_1.pdf
- [71] Office for Nuclear Regulation, “Outcomes of nuclear AI regulatory sandbox pilot published,” Nov. 2023.
- [72] A. White and J. Surman, “Progressing Regulation of AI in the Nuclear Sector,” in *AI4Nuclear Workshop*, Oct. 2024. [Online]. Available: https://www.gen-4.org/sites/default/files/2024-10/20241018%20Progressing%20Regulation%20of%20AI%20in%20the%20Nuclear%20Sector%20-%20AI4Nuclear%20Workshop%20FINAL_1.pdf
- [73] Office for Nuclear Regulation; U.S. Nuclear Regulatory Commission; Canadian Nuclear Safety Commission, “Considerations for Developing Artificial Intelligence Systems in Nuclear Applications,” Sep. 2024. Accessed: Apr. 29, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nrc.gov/docs/ML2424/ML24241A252.pdf>
- [74] L. L. Churchill, “Cooperation on Artificial Intelligence: CANUKUS AI Principles,” Dec. 2024, *Canadian Nuclear Safety Commission*. [Online]. Available: https://www.wins.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/E-DOCS-7420167-v2-CANUKUS_AI_Paper_WINS_Briefing_2024-12.pdf

Appendix A: WP6 Analysis of WP3 Identified Regulatory Issues

A-1 *Issue 1: Lack of Unified Definition for Problematic Waste*

“Only respondents from UK and France have an internal (within organization) unified definition for problematic wastes ensuring alignment across departments or stakeholders involved in waste management processes. Therefore, it may be concluded that most of the organization are waiting for national/supra-national legislation or the world's centres for cooperation in the nuclear field to take over a definition of problematic waste.

[...] there is potential, and opportunities based on potential common definition of PW, an harmonisation on waste inventory.”

“European countries in terms of waste classification implement the EU directives, or international recommendations for waste classification (e.g. IAEA's Safety Standards Series No. GSG-1/2009; EC council directive 2011/70/EURATOM). Therefore, it is necessary to address and define the ‘problematic waste’ on this supra-national level.”

“The benefits of potential harmonized RAW classification system are understood mainly as easier comparison, benchmarking and exchange of information on RAW management practices within Europe. Nevertheless, there are other expected benefits as e.g. facilitating of using existing processing facilities across Europe; paving the way toward a harmonized international waste processing and disposal system.”

Classification: Regulatory Issue

Analysis:

This issue was classified as regulatory because it reflects a lack of alignment with existing standards and the absence of enforceable, harmonized definitions at the EU or international level. The report makes clear that only a minority of countries (UK and France) have an internal, organization-wide definition of problematic waste. As a result, inconsistencies persist across stakeholders, leading to fragmentation in waste classification, inventory development, and treatment strategies. A standardized, supra-national definition is considered essential for enabling cooperation, mutual understanding, and efficient use of treatment infrastructure across MS.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

A-2 Issue 2: Differences in National Waste Classification Standards

“European countries in terms of waste classification implement the EU directives, or international recommendations for waste classification (e.g. IAEA's Safety Standards Series No. GSG-1/2009; EC council directive 2011/70/EURATOM). Therefore, it is necessary to address and define the ‘problematic waste’ on this supra-national level.”

Classification: Regulatory Issue

Analysis:

This issue relates to the structural divergence in how Member States implement classification systems, with some relying on EU guidance, others on IAEA standards, and still others applying outdated or country-specific frameworks. The analysis recognizes the importance of defining problematic waste consistently and indicates that harmonized classification would enable better comparison, benchmarking, and exchange of practices. In the absence of such alignment, mutual recognition of waste categories remains difficult, hindering both domestic and cross-border treatment efforts.

A-3 Issue 4: Legal and Administrative Barriers to Cross-Border Cooperation

“The main obstacle in terms of cross-border cooperation (treatment and conditioning of waste) considered by the respondents is whether the country's legislation allows the RAW export for processing or the import of other countries' RAW for processing and conditioning.”

“Majority of respondents' countries has legislation to cover the export/import of radioactive waste to or from other EU Member State; however, there is room for enhancement of lines of communication for cross-border cooperation.”

Classification: Perceived Issue

Analysis:

Although initially identified by stakeholders as a barrier, this issue was categorized as a perceived issue upon closer analysis. The document points out that most countries do have legal provisions in place for the import and export of radioactive waste. The

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

real barrier lies in inconsistent interpretation, insufficient communication, and unclear administrative practices rather than in the absence of legislation. Existing successful case studies (e.g. La Hague, Cycle Life) demonstrate that effective cross-border cooperation is possible when legal frameworks are understood and applied consistently.

A-4 Issue 5: Lack of Harmonized Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC)

“Compliance with the Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC) must be declared to the Regulator for disposal at the appropriate facility/repository. WAC have not been developed for some types of waste's final disposal.”

Perceived issue. This issue seems to refer to the obligation to take back waste generated by cross-border treatment facilities or services. It is true, particularly with regard to LILW or HLW waste, that disposal facilities are still in development in Europe and do not have WAC or only preliminary ones. However, examples of treatment facilities, such as La Hague in France for Spent Fuel, show that the absence of WAC does not prevent the return of LILW or HLW in the country of origin.”

Classification: Perceived Issue

Analysis:

This issue reflects a commonly held assumption that the absence of fully developed WAC represents a legal or regulatory barrier. However, the report clarifies that WAC may be incomplete or preliminary for some waste types, and yet treatment and return of waste still occur in practice. This difference between perception and reality qualifies the issue as “perceived,” suggesting that the challenge is more about stakeholder understanding than regulatory absence. The case of La Hague is cited as proof that operational and regulatory pathways can exist even when WAC are under development.

A-5 Issue 8: Diverging Legal Interpretations of Hazardous RAW

“In all MS [...], wastes are classified as hazardous separately from their radiological classification; [...]. Some MS indicated that regulations applicable to the management of radioactive wastes and regulations applicable to the management of hazardous are

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

applied in parallel (i.e. Belgium, Sweden, and Lithuania). In other countries (such as the UK, France, Denmark and Czech Republic) radioactive waste legislation is considered to apply to wastes that are both radioactive and hazardous. [...], there is discrepancy in the manner of addressing the applicable regulations (parallel application of RAW legislation and hazardous waste legislation/ only radioactive waste legislation). For strengthening of the cross-border cooperation, the fewer authorities and legislation sources are included the easier the process is [...]. Therefore, it seems appropriate to examine the possibility of EU to set the definition and liability for hazardous RAW within the RAW legislation.”

Classification: Regulatory Issue

Analysis:

The inconsistency in how countries classify and regulate hazardous radioactive waste is identified as a barrier to streamlined management. In some MS, hazardous RAW is managed under both hazardous waste and radioactive waste regulations; in others, it is treated under a single framework. This variation complicates cross-border cooperation, as differing legal interpretations can slow down or block treatment, transport, or disposal approvals. A harmonized definition and regulatory treatment under EU law would reduce these inconsistencies and facilitate cooperation.

A-6 Issue 9: Societal and Political Constraints on Waste Management

“Nations set different priorities for managing nuclear waste based on political, environmental or public concerns. Strong public opposition can delay or block the establishment of waste treatment facilities.”

Strategic issue. This issue seems to relate to prioritization. Priorities linked to nuclear waste management should be addressed in National Plan. Public participation mechanisms may also be addressed in National Plan.

“Some countries may not have clear policies or sufficient infrastructure to handle waste, leading to delays or inaction.”

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

→ Strategic issue. This issue relates to resource allocation and prioritization in order to favour waste management facilities implementation. It underlines the need for wider implementation of cross-border services or facilities.”

“The importance of the regulator engagement in the alignment of the wastes with treatment technologies is well understood also by the intergovernmental agencies and forums [...].”

→ Strategic issue. This issue relates to prioritization through regulator engagement in order to favour cross-border treatments for specific waste.”

“Regulator/ legislation [...] shall understand and support ‘Recycling and Reuse’ approach [...].”

→ Strategic issue. This issue relates to prioritization in order to favour waste recycling.”

Classification: Strategic Issue

Analysis:

This issue encompasses political, public, and institutional factors that influence waste management decisions. The document identifies public opposition, unclear national priorities, and lack of regulatory engagement as key contributors to delays in establishing treatment infrastructure. These are not legal or technical challenges but rather matters of prioritization, communication, and planning—hence the strategic classification. Addressing these constraints requires national-level action, integrated planning, and sustained regulator involvement in both technical and public-facing roles.

A-7 Issue 10: Lack of Treatment Infrastructure for Hazardous RAW

“As there are several types of hazardous RAW with no established route for their management, having been stored and awaiting the establishment of management options. There is room for uniform approaches, cooperation in definitions and designs, even erection and use of common facilities for hazardous RAW within Europe.”

Classification: Technical Issue

Analysis:

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

The absence of treatment infrastructure for certain hazardous RAW types is not tied to legal or policy deficiencies but to technical capacity. These waste streams are being stored with no clear route to final management. The report identifies an opportunity for Member States to collaborate on the design, construction, and use of shared facilities — especially where national options are limited. This makes it a technical issue, highlighting a tangible gap in infrastructure rather than a breakdown in regulation or strategy.

Appendix B: WP6 Analysis of WP4 Identified Regulatory Issues

Decommissioning nuclear facilities in a way that aligns with circular economy principles (reuse, recycling, waste minimization) faces several challenges. In particular, the process of clearance – releasing materials from radiological control for conventional use – and broader radioactive material management is constrained by regulatory frameworks and practical considerations. Below, we evaluate ten key issues in this domain. Each issue is classified as primarily regulatory, technical, strategic, or perceived, based on the nature of the challenge, and justified with evidence. A summary classification table is provided for quick reference.

Issue	Classification
1. Inconsistent Transposition of EU Directive 2013/59	Regulatory issue (gap/conflict in law)
2. Overly Stringent and Non-Risk-Based Approaches	Regulatory issue (overly strict implementation)
3. Complex and Costly Clearance Procedures	Regulatory issue (procedural burden)
4. Narrow Focus on Radiological Aspects	Strategic issue (lack of holistic approach)
5. Traceability Requirements Impede Recycling	Regulatory issue (well-intended, but counterproductive)
6. Lack of Coherence between Nuclear and Conventional Waste Systems	Regulatory issue (framework mismatch)
7. Lack of Support for Multicriteria and Life-Cycle Analysis	Strategic issue (planning/decision-making gap)
8. Inflexible Application of the Waste Management Hierarchy	Strategic issue (policy/implementation approach)
9. Outdated Technical Guidance (e.g., RP89 and RP122)	Technical issue (outdated standards)
10. Need for EC-Endorsed Tools and Guidance	Technical issue (tool/methodology gap)

B-1 Inconsistent Transposition of EU Directive 2013/59

Classification: Regulatory issue (gap in uniform implementation of law)

Variations in how EU Member States implement clearance levels for materials arising from nuclear decommissioning have resulted in differences that may complicate the cross-border movement of recyclable materials. While EU guidance documents offer a framework, their non-binding nature allows for national interpretation, leading to diverse regulatory practices. For instance, France uses a zoning approach that precludes clearance, whereas countries like Germany and Sweden have established radionuclide-specific limits and conditional clearance pathways. Since 1996, some regulations have become more detailed, but in many cases also more conservative, with lower clearance thresholds for key radionuclides such as Cs-137 and Co-60. The OECD NEA has noted that this ongoing lack of regulatory alignment can create

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

practical challenges for recycling and reuse, as well as for building stakeholder confidence [30].

B-2 Overly Stringent and Non-Risk-Based Approaches

Classification: Regulatory issue (overly strict implementation beyond what risk warrants)

Radiation protection regulations are intended to be risk-informed, focusing efforts where they provide meaningful safety benefits. However, in the context of decommissioning, stakeholders have raised concerns that some national regulatory approaches apply standards that are stricter than necessary, resulting in disproportionate requirements for cleanup or oversight.

International bodies such as the IAEA and the ICRP consider annual public exposures on the order of 10 μSv as trivial and of no regulatory concern [51], [52]. In a truly risk-based framework, achieving this dose level should be sufficient for the clearance or release of materials. Nevertheless, in practice, some regulators enforce more conservative thresholds or add control layers that are not proportionate to the actual radiological hazard.

One contributing factor is the interpretation of the ALARA principle (As Low As Reasonably Achievable). While ALARA is meant to guide decision-making by balancing safety, cost, and practicality, it is sometimes applied as “as low as possible,” ignoring diminishing returns in risk reduction [53]. This can lead to excessive costs, delays, and resource use with little or no measurable public health benefit.

Another driver is public perception. The IAEA notes that the public often views any radiation as harmful, even at trivial levels. This misunderstanding may lead regulators to maintain highly conservative policies to preserve public confidence, despite scientific consensus on acceptable risk thresholds.

In summary, while safety must remain the priority, some regulatory practices in decommissioning are not fully aligned with modern risk-informed standards. Aligning national regulations with internationally endorsed thresholds— such as the 10

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

$\mu\text{Sv}/\text{year}$ benchmark — could improve efficiency and clarity without compromising safety.

B-3 Complex and Costly Clearance Procedures

Classification: Regulatory issue (procedural/implementation burden with technical challenges)

Clearance procedures for releasing materials from nuclear regulatory control — particularly during decommissioning — are often complex and resource-intensive. Although international guidance such as from the IAEA exists, approaches vary across countries. Differing clearance levels, measurement protocols, and documentation requirements hinder mutual recognition of clearance decisions, causing duplicated efforts and higher costs [30]. The World Nuclear Association highlights that “clearance levels differ internationally, leaving scope for greater harmonization,” while the OECD NEA notes that recycling from nuclear decommissioning continues to grow despite this lack of harmonisation [30].

A key inconsistency lies in clearance thresholds. For example, steel scrap from gas plants can be exempted if radioactivity is below 500,000 Bq/kg — 1,000 times higher than the 500 Bq/kg clearance level typically applied to recycled material from the nuclear industry. The EC proposed clearance levels of 10 MBq/kg for Fe-55 and Ni-63 in 1996, while the IAEA proposed lower limits of 0.3 and 3 MBq/kg respectively. For mixed radionuclides, a weighted summation of activity against nuclide-specific limits must be applied [30].

This disparity contributes to emerging double standards. In Europe, dose constraints for non-nuclear recycled material range from 0.3 to 1.0 mSv/year, whereas nuclear materials are subject to just 0.01 mSv/year. This means the same radionuclide, at the same concentration, can be either reused or sent for deep disposal depending solely on its origin. Norway and the Netherlands are the only countries applying consistent standards. For example, Ra-226 — common in oil and gas scrap with a 1600-year half-life — can be cleared at 500 Bq/kg under a 0.3 mSv/year dose constraint. In contrast, similar nuclear scrap containing shorter-lived Co-60 or Cs-137 may face clearance levels as low as 10 Bq/kg [30].

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

These inconsistencies complicate international recycling. In 2011, Bruce Power (Canada) planned to ship 16 decommissioned steam generators to Sweden for recycling. Each generator, 100 tonnes in weight, contained only ~4 g of radionuclides (340 GBq total) and a surface dose rate of 0.08 mSv/h. Although approved by the Canadian Nuclear Safety Commission as a safe, responsible waste management practice, the plan was shelved following the Fukushima incident due to public opposition. In contrast, Studsvik successfully recycled similar components from UK plants, and by 2015 had processed and cleared over 40,000 tonnes of various metals, recycling more than 90% [30]. In the U.S., EnergySolutions recycled over 62,000 tonnes of mostly ferrous metals under similar programs.

However, such efforts are limited by fragmented clearance frameworks. Smaller operators, in particular, face difficulty navigating multiple inconsistent regimes. Harmonisation and risk-based clearance approaches could reduce regulatory burdens, cut costs, and improve recycling efficiency—while maintaining high safety standards.

B-4 Narrow Focus on Radiological Aspects

Classification: Strategic issue (lack of holistic, multi-criteria approach)

Traditionally, clearance regulations in nuclear decommissioning focus almost exclusively on radiological safety — ensuring that residual radioactivity remains below defined thresholds to protect human health and the environment. While this is essential, the approach is narrow when viewed through the lens of sustainability and circular economy goals.

In practice, decisions on whether to recycle or dispose of materials tend to hinge solely on activity concentration. If levels are below regulatory limits, clearance is granted; if not, the material is treated as radioactive waste. There is typically no framework requiring consideration of other important factors such as environmental impact, carbon footprint, resource conservation, or economic and social benefits. This isn't a legal limitation — no laws prohibit broader consideration — but rather a cultural or strategic gap in decision-making.

The current opinion of this single-criterion approach is that it could lead to suboptimal outcomes. For example, slightly contaminated metal that marginally exceeds

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

clearance limits is often disposed of, even if controlled melting and recycling would yield environmental benefits with negligible radiological risk. The absence of multicriteria evaluation means opportunities for more sustainable solutions may be missed.

Stakeholders have highlighted the need to include “other than radiological protection and nuclear safety aspects” in decommissioning decisions. Factors such as life-cycle environmental impact, economic value, and social acceptability should be integrated into clearance strategies.

This gap reflects a strategic issue — not a regulatory flaw but a lack of guidance and planning methodology. Moving forward, regulators and operators should adopt multicriteria decision analysis (MCDA) [54] and life-cycle assessment (LCA) [55] tools to balance radiological safety with broader sustainability indicators. Safety remains paramount, but once radiological thresholds are met, decisions should ask: What is the best overall option for this material?

Case studies show that MCDA approaches can support better decisions and highlight the need for a “global approach” to managing very low-level materials. Expanding the decision framework in this way is key to realizing a true circular economy in the nuclear sector.

B-5 Traceability Requirements Impede Recycling

Classification: Regulatory issue (well-intended control that can be counterproductive)

Balancing the objectives of safety, accountability, and sustainability is crucial in the context of recycling materials from nuclear facilities. While traceability requirements are designed to ensure the safe handling of materials, evidence suggests that overly stringent regulations may inadvertently hinder recycling efforts. For example, the OECD Nuclear Energy Agency reports that “stakeholder issues such as social/industry acceptance, perception of risk, politics/government intervention and lack of confidence/understanding are still significant obstacles” to recycling and reuse, with traceability requirements contributing to increased costs and administrative burdens.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

U.S. Nuclear Regulatory Commission has identified deficiencies in material traceability and control, particularly concerning fasteners, highlighting the potential operational safety implications of inadequate traceability systems. However, challenges in maintaining effective traceability systems have also been noted, suggesting that overly stringent traceability requirements might introduce inefficiencies [56].

Therefore, a nuanced approach is warranted—one that maintains rigorous safety standards while streamlining traceability requirements to facilitate recycling. This could involve risk-informed regulatory adjustments, such as waiving traceability for materials well below clearance thresholds and enhancing public communication to build trust and understanding. Such measures aim to harmonize safety, environmental sustainability, and economic efficiency in the management of materials from nuclear facilities.

B-6 Lack of Coherence between Nuclear and Conventional Waste Governance

Classification: Regulatory issue (mismatch and gaps between different regulatory frameworks)

The nuclear industry operates under a distinct framework for classifying and managing radioactive waste, encompassing categories such as low-level, intermediate-level, and high-level waste. In contrast, the conventional waste management sector addresses industrial, municipal, and hazardous wastes within a separate regulatory structure. This separation can lead to challenges when materials transition between these sectors, particularly during the decommissioning of nuclear facilities. Materials that have been "cleared" — deemed to have radioactivity levels below regulatory concern — may still encounter acceptance issues from conventional waste management facilities. This reluctance often stems from regulatory discrepancies and a lack of harmonization between nuclear and environmental authorities. For example, a steel component from a decommissioned reactor that meets clearance criteria might technically be safe for recycling. However, conventional recyclers may hesitate to accept such materials due to unfamiliarity with clearance procedures or because their operating permits do not account for materials originating from nuclear sites. This lack of coherence between conventional and nuclear waste oversight can hinder the

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

integration of cleared materials into conventional recycling streams, posing obstacles to circular economy initiatives.

An example of regulatory adjustment aimed at addressing the lack of coherence between nuclear and conventional waste systems is the case of the Joint Research Centre (JRC) Ispra site in Italy. On October 29, 2024, the Italian Nuclear Regulator (ISIN) approved a new clearance procedure that allows certain materials from nuclear installations to be reclassified as conventional waste—provided they meet strict radiological safety criteria. This step was taken to reduce the amount of material unnecessarily treated as radioactive, thereby lowering decommissioning costs and supporting environmental and circular economy goals [57].

Tackling these challenges would benefit from greater alignment between nuclear and conventional waste regulatory frameworks. Improving communication and developing clearer acceptance criteria—alongside broader recognition of clearance processes—could help support the safe recycling and reuse of materials from decommissioned nuclear sites. Such steps would contribute to environmental sustainability efforts and advance circular economy objectives.

B-7 Lack of Support for Multicriteria and Life-Cycle Analysis

Classification: Strategic issue (methodological and planning gap)

This issue continues the discussion on broadening the basis for decision-making in nuclear decommissioning. While there is agreement that choices should account for more than radiological safety — such as cost, environmental impact, and socio-economic effects — there is limited support for applying tools like multicriteria analysis (MCA) and life-cycle analysis (LCA) in practice.

There are no legal barriers to using these methods. However, they are not included in standard regulatory procedures, and there is little formal guidance or expectation for their use. Some organizations choose to use them. For example, the UK Nuclear Decommissioning Authority (NDA) uses a Value Framework to assess site end-states based on safety, cost, environmental performance, and social value. But this approach is not widely adopted across other countries or supported at the European level [58].

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

A global study of 162 decommissioning projects [59] found that decisions such as whether to dismantle immediately or defer the work are shaped by many technical and non-technical factors. Despite this, structured use of MCA or LCA was rarely observed, even though the methods are available and usable. An EU-wide survey also found that while many countries ask for a justification of strategy, only a few provide formal tools or instructions for how to compare options. In many cases, decisions are based on engineering judgment or established practice, rather than structured analysis.

This represents a policy and implementation gap. Without official support, operators may be reluctant to present arguments that balance radiological and non-radiological considerations. For example, they may avoid proposing reuse of slightly contaminated materials, even if it offers environmental or cost benefits, due to uncertainty about regulatory acceptance.

This gap could be addressed without changing laws. What is needed is practical guidance, shared methods, and training to support the use of MCA and LCA. Clear signals from regulators that these approaches are acceptable would also encourage their wider use. This would help ensure that decisions reflect a broader set of priorities, including resource efficiency and sustainability.

B-8 Inflexible Application of the Waste Management Hierarchy

Classification: Strategic issue (rigid policy application that may conflict with optimal outcomes)

The waste management hierarchy — prioritizing prevention, reuse, recycling, recovery, and disposal as a last resort — is a foundational principle in environmental policy. Applying this hierarchy to radioactive materials during nuclear decommissioning presents challenges, particularly when radiological safety considerations lead to rigid interpretations that may conflict with environmental sustainability goals.

At the Trawsfynydd nuclear power station in North Wales, the decommissioning strategy evolved from deferred reactor dismantling to continuous dismantling. This shift aimed to expedite decommissioning activities, resulting in significant changes to the site's skyline. While this approach considered the waste hierarchy by potentially reducing waste volumes and aligning with broader environmental objectives, it also

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

highlighted the complexities of balancing safety with environmental considerations [60].

Despite such examples, the application of the waste hierarchy in nuclear decommissioning is not consistently implemented across all projects. In some instances, the emphasis on achieving the lowest possible levels of residual radioactivity leads to the removal and disposal of materials that could otherwise be safely reused or recycled. This approach can result in increased environmental impacts due to the unnecessary generation of waste.

Stakeholders have highlighted the need for greater flexibility to facilitate the reuse or recycling of materials, tools, or buildings during decommissioning. They suggest that this can be achieved through guidance supported by regulators, rather than changes to the overarching legal framework. This implies that while the waste hierarchy is a sound principle, its practical application requires more nuanced and context-specific strategies.

The inflexible application of the waste management hierarchy in nuclear decommissioning underscores the need for integrated decision-making that balances radiological safety with environmental sustainability. By adopting a more flexible, case-by-case approach — underpinned by multicriteria decision analysis— decommissioning projects can better adhere to the waste hierarchy, minimizing waste generation and favouring reuse and recycling without compromising safety.

B-9 Outdated Technical Guidance (e.g., RP89 and RP122)

Classification: Technical issue (obsolete standards and data in use)

The EC's Radiation Protection guidance documents, RP-89 and RP-122, published in the late 1990s and early 2000s, established clearance levels for materials arising from the decommissioning of nuclear facilities. However, these documents have not been substantially updated to reflect advancements in scientific understanding or operational experience gained over the past two decades. For example, RP-122 specifies unconditional clearance levels of 0.1 Bq/g for cobalt-60 (Co-60) and 1 Bq/g for caesium-137 (Cs-137). More recently, the Basic Safety Standards Directive (2013/59/Euratom) proposes an unconditional clearance level of 0.1 Bq/g for Cs-137,

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

aligning it with that of Co-60. While intended to enhance radiological safety, this lower threshold presents practical challenges in demonstrating compliance and may result in increased volumes of materials being classified as radioactive waste requiring disposal. These developments have occurred despite earlier concerns that clearance levels were already overly conservative, and they risk further limiting the feasibility of recycling and reuse pathways for slightly contaminated materials [30].

This stagnation can lead to overly conservative practices, potentially hindering efficient decommissioning and recycling efforts. Stakeholders have expressed the need for updates to these documents to incorporate new data, such as revised dose coefficients and feedback from decommissioning projects. Without such revisions, current practices may continue to rely on outdated scientific understanding, limiting the scope of material reuse and recycling in the nuclear industry.

In summary, updating RP-89 and RP-122 is essential to align clearance practices with contemporary scientific knowledge and operational insights, thereby facilitating more effective and sustainable decommissioning processes.

B-10 Need for EC-Endorsed Tools and Guidance

Classification: Technical issue (lack of practical tools/methods support)

Stakeholders in the nuclear decommissioning sector have identified a significant need for EC -endorsed tools and guidance to standardize clearance calculations and waste management practices, particularly to support circular economy initiatives. Currently, the absence of such standardized tools leads individual countries or operators to develop their own methods for demonstrating compliance with clearance levels, resulting in inconsistencies and inefficiencies. The development of an EU-wide software tool for clearance calculations, officially endorsed by the EC, would provide a uniform platform for calculating residual activity, doses, and clearance compliance, thereby reducing uncertainty and expediting regulatory acceptance. This need is underscored by the outdated nature of existing guidance documents, such as the Radiation Protection series reports RP-89 and RP-122, published in the late 1990s and early 2000s, which have not been updated to reflect advancements in science and operational experience. An EC-endorsed tool could harmonize practices across

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

Member States, aligning with the goal of consistency and facilitating the application of clearance and waste hierarchy principles in a more efficient and standardized manner.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

Appendix C :WP6 Analysis of WP5 Identified Regulatory Issues

Implementing Digital Twins, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Robotics, and Building Information Modelling (BIM) in nuclear decommissioning promises significant safety and efficiency gains. However, the HARPERS WP5 analysis reveals a spectrum of potential regulatory hurdles impeding these innovations. Below, we detail six key challenge clusters – from unclear guidance to international inconsistencies – and provide for each an executive summary, discussion of issues, existing regulations, global best practices, root causes, and actionable solutions for regulators, policymakers, and technology developers.

C-1 Regulatory Clarity, Guidance, and Frameworks

Summary:

Regulatory guidance specific to advanced technologies in decommissioning is generally not readily available. First-of-a-kind (FOAK) solutions may face ambiguous or piecemeal requirements, as no dedicated frameworks exist for AI, digital twins, or BIM in the nuclear sector. Early engagement between implementers/providers and regulators is not routine. Such challenges slow the adoption of new tools and can increase costs.

Issues & Implications:

Nuclear regulations traditionally focus on proven methods; as a result, FOAK technologies encounter unclear approval pathways. Documentation is spread across nuclear safety, radiation protection, industrial safety, and environmental regulations, which may not explicitly address novel digital tools or robotics. For example, implementers report that regulatory uncertainty and inconsistent interpretations across documents cause delays. The absence of official guidance on AI-driven systems or digital twins means each project must negotiate requirements case-by-case, risking project delays or conservative approaches that dilute innovation benefits. Ambiguity around what evidence is needed for acceptance (e.g. how to qualify a machine-learning algorithm or a VR-based simulator) leaves both developers and regulators in a difficult position.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

Existing Regulations:

At present, no comprehensive nuclear regulatory framework specifically covers AI or digital twin applications in decommissioning. Regulators rely on general nuclear safety principles (e.g. IAEA safety standards, national nuclear facility regulations) and on analogous frameworks (such as software qualification guidelines for instrumentation). For instance, the U.S. Nuclear Regulatory Commission (NRC) has begun identifying potential regulatory framework gaps for AI and digital twins, acknowledging that existing rules do not explicitly encompass these technologies [61]. Likewise, European regulators have not issued dedicated rules for BIM or robotics in decommissioning – any references are indirect (for example, general requirements for controlling industrial devices or computer-based systems). This regulatory silence means implementers must infer requirements from broader regulations (like quality assurance for software, or safety case expectations) without tailored guidance, contributing to uncertainty.

International Benchmarks & Best Practices:

International nuclear bodies are starting to recognize this gap. The NRC has conducted future-focused research and public meetings on digital twin regulatory considerations, producing technical letters on challenges and considerations for digital twins in nuclear applications. These efforts, while not yet formal rules, at least document how regulators might approach the technology. Another example is the UK's Office for Nuclear Regulation (ONR) launching an Innovation Hub and sandbox to proactively study AI regulation, effectively writing the playbook as they go [62]. Such initiatives serve as de facto guidance: they clarify expectations through case studies, even in absence of codified regulations. Outside the nuclear field, sectors like medicine and automotive have issued AI/automation guidelines (e.g. FDA's software guidelines, automotive functional safety standards) – these can inspire nuclear regulators to craft analogous guidance for decommissioning technology.

Key Barriers and Root Causes:

The root cause is a policy lag – technology is advancing faster than regulations. Regulators are understandably cautious; without prior examples, they have not yet developed rules for these tools. This leads to a “chicken-and-egg” problem:

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

implementers/providers may hesitate to invest without clear regulatory support, and regulators wait for proven cases before developing guidance. Additionally, regulatory documentation is fragmented across domains (nuclear safety, worker safety, environmental rules), making it hard to see the full picture. A lack of early dialogue exacerbates challenges, e.g., developers may design a digital system under assumptions that later conflict with regulatory interpretations. In short, neither side has a clear reference point, and each FOAK project must blaze a new trail. This not only slows specific projects but also fails to generate standardized knowledge for future use.

Solutions and Recommendations:

Establishing clearer frameworks and guidance is important. Policymakers and regulators should create dedicated guidance notes or standards for advanced technology in decommissioning (e.g. an IAEA Safety Guide on digital instrumentation in decommissioning, or national regulatory position papers on AI use). Early engagement mechanisms – such as pre-application consultations or regulatory sandboxes – should be institutionalized so that innovators can get feedback on proposed technologies before formal licensing [62]. Regulators can also issue “roadmaps” for FOAK approvals, outlining stepwise expectations (for example, how to demonstrate an AI’s reliability or how to integrate BIM models into decommissioning plans). Technology developers are advised to involve regulatory experts from the outset and to align their documentation (safety analyses, validation reports) with the language of existing regulatory principles, even if specific guidance is missing. Over time, lessons from one FOAK deployment should be codified into guidance for the next – a continuous learning loop. International forums (ENSREG in Europe, IAEA globally) can help by sharing case studies of how specific advanced technology deployments were regulated, thereby developing a body of precedent that effectively becomes guidance. Ultimately, clarity will improve if regulators proactively articulate how new technologies can meet underlying safety objectives, rather than leaving each proponent to interpret these on their own. This clarity reduces uncertainty, encouraging innovation while maintaining safety.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

C-2 *Adaptation to Technological Innovation*

Summary:

Nuclear regulatory regimes may struggle to adapt at the pace of technological innovation. Requirements can be overly prescriptive or not proportionate to risk, meaning novel solutions are held to standards developed for older methods. Rigid waste processing and disposal criteria may not accommodate new techniques, and the regulatory update cycle is slow, lagging behind fast-evolving digital and robotic tools. These challenges can discourage beneficial innovations or render them impractical despite safety advantages.

Issues & Implications:

One challenge is that some regulatory requirements are not sufficiently risk-informed or performance-based to readily allow for new technology. For example, if a robot can reduce worker dose in a demolition task, in principle regulators could welcome it – but if rules demand the robot meet the exact same qualification processes as a safety-class system (regardless of the modest risk it introduces), the cost or time can outweigh the benefit. In practice, stakeholders observe that regulation is sometimes applied uniformly rather than proportionately to the risk reduction a technology brings. Rigid compliance checklists can thus inadvertently penalize innovative approaches. Another issue is static waste acceptance and environmental standards: disposal criteria (for waste packages, materials clearance, etc.) were written with traditional techniques in mind. When new treatment methods produce novel waste forms (e.g. a recycled material or an additive-manufactured plug), existing standards might lack criteria to accept them, effectively blocking their use. Similarly, if regulations mandate certain waste processing routes, using a more efficient robotics-assisted route might require time-consuming exemptions or changes. Lastly, the long cycle for regulatory development means guidelines might only be updated once a decade or in reaction to major events. In a field like AI or digital modelling, which advances yearly, regulators find themselves reacting rather than guiding. As a result, promising technologies may remain in regulatory uncertainty for extended periods, delaying realisation of their potential benefits and possibly discouraging innovation within critical sectors like nuclear safety and decommissioning.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

Existing Regulations:

Historically, nuclear regulatory frameworks were prescriptive – e.g. specifying approved methods for decontamination or dismantling. Many jurisdictions are now shifting towards risk-informed, performance-based regulation, but progress varies. The IAEA General Safety Requirements call for a graded approach: controls commensurate with the hazard. While this principle is recognized on paper, its practical implementation for new technology is inconsistent. Some regulators (like the U.S. NRC) have initiated rule revisions to be more technology-inclusive (the NRC’s proposed Part 53 rule aims to be risk-informed and performance-based for new reactors [63], but equivalent initiatives in decommissioning and waste management are still in an early stage of development. Waste disposal standards (e.g. waste acceptance criteria in each country) are typically stringent and rule-based, with few provisions for flexibility – they ensure safety but can lack mechanisms for case-by-case adaptation. There are also non-nuclear regulations that affect decommissioning technology: for instance, industrial robotics safety standards or civil aviation rules (for drones). These tend to be updated more frequently and could influence nuclear use of such technology, but nuclear regulators must then reconcile those with nuclear-specific requirements. In summary, the regulatory framework exists but is often static, and special permissions or amendments are required to deviate, which is a slow process.

International Benchmarks & Case Studies:

A promising practice is the use of regulatory sandbox programs to pilot innovative methods under regulator observation. The UK, for example, ran a pilot sandbox for AI applications in nuclear, allowing regulators and industry to jointly explore how to regulate a novel AI solution in a controlled setting. This sandbox – the first in the nuclear sector – helped identify proportionate regulatory approaches for AI, rather than defaulting to rigid compliance, and the outcomes are informing broader guidance. Internationally, the OECD Nuclear Energy Agency’s new RegLab initiative is explicitly focused on enabling agile regulation for emerging technology (initially AI for reactors) by using sandbox exercises and collaborative trials [64]. These efforts illustrate an agile regulatory mindset: “test before you codify.” Another example of adaptation is in waste management: some countries have adopted a case-by-case regulatory review

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

for innovative waste forms. For instance, Belgium and the UK have, in specific cases, allowed treatment of waste by novel processes followed by a tailored assessment to ensure disposal safety, rather than an outright prohibition due to lack of precedent. While time-consuming, these case studies build a knowledge base that can be generalized. Additionally, risk-informed decision-making practices are being integrated – the U.S. NRC has extensive guidance on risk-informed approaches for materials and waste [65], which, if applied, could allow scaling requirements to the actual risk of a given technology deployment. The key benchmark is regulatory agility: sectors like aerospace have introduced special processes to quickly certify innovations (e.g. experimental certifications). The nuclear field is cautiously moving in that direction through these pilot programs.

Key Barriers and Root Causes:

The fundamental barrier is institutional inertia and cultural conservatism. Nuclear safety regulators, for good reason, prioritize proven safety and may default to conservative requirements “just in case,” even if a new method might arguably warrant a different approach. This can lead to over-specification, where a low-risk trial of a robot faces the same documentation burden as a major plant modification. Another root cause is the lack of built-in flexibility in regulations – many rules were written when the technological landscape was static, so they lack clauses for innovative equivalences or waivers. For example, waste criteria may have fixed limits that do not consider alternative verification methods; changing them involves lengthy rulemaking or license amendments. Regulatory agencies often have limited resources to proactively research new technologies, leading to a slow, reactive process for updating rules. Developing new regulations, such as consensus standards and rulemaking, can take years. By the time these regulations are published, technological advancements may have already surpassed them. Additionally, when regulatory bodies operate in isolated silos—such as nuclear, environmental, and industrial safety regulators each enforcing strict rules within their specific areas—it can result in conflicting or redundant requirements. This fragmented structure particularly burdens innovative approaches. For instance, a new waste processing robot might have to satisfy nuclear safety regulators (for reliability), radiation protection regulators (for dose control), and

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

environmental regulators (for waste outputs) without a unified risk picture – and none have a streamlined process for something unprecedented.

Solutions and Recommendations:

To better adapt to innovation, regulators could consider more risk-informed, agile regulatory processes. Concretely, this means expanding initiatives like regulatory sandboxes or pilot authorization programs. Regulators and government could fund and support sandbox trials where innovators can deploy new technology under supervision, gathering real data to inform flexible regulation. The insights from these pilots can then feed into formal guidance or even expedited licensing pathways for similar cases. Policymakers can enable this by ensuring legal frameworks allow regulators to grant time-limited experimental permits without full compliance, provided safety is maintained. Additionally, regulators could update or reinterpret standards to incorporate graded approaches: for each new technology proposal, ask how its risks differ from traditional methods and scale regulatory oversight accordingly. For example, if a digital twin is used only for simulation and does not control equipment, regulatory oversight can focus on data security and quality, not on the full safety system qualification that an operational control system would need. In the waste realm, flexibility in waste acceptance criteria (WAC) could be considered – perhaps via an “innovative waste form” review process that can qualify new waste forms for disposal if an equivalent safety case is demonstrated. This might involve interim criteria or a fast-track evaluation by the waste disposal authority, rather than waiting for WAC documents to be formally revised (which could take years). Regulatory agencies are encouraged to shorten their update cycles by using modular guidance (issuing technical position papers or interim staff guidance that can be published more rapidly than formal rules). Older requirements could be systematically reviewed to identify those that are overly conservative or prescriptive and could be made to be performance-based. For instance, if a rule states “technology X must be used,” it could be changed to indicate “performance Y must be achieved,” thereby allowing alternative technology, where applicable, to meet the same safety goal. Industry developers should proactively provide risk evidence to regulators – for example, show through analysis or small-scale trials that a new method meets safety goals with equal or

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

greater margin, to make the case for regulatory accommodation. Joint workshops and working groups between regulators, operators, and technology suppliers can help update standards in synchrony with innovation (as seen in NEA's RegLab for AI). Ultimately, by making regulation more agile – without sacrificing safety – the nuclear sector can better integrate cutting-edge tools that improve decommissioning outcomes.

C-3 *Awareness and Understanding of Regulatory Requirements*

Summary:

Many technology developers and vendors entering the nuclear decommissioning arena face a knowledge gap regarding the nuclear regulatory framework. The specialized requirements – from quality assurance to licensing procedures – can be poorly understood by those outside the traditional nuclear supply chain. This lack of awareness leads to compliance mistakes, delays, or reluctance to engage in nuclear projects. Improving mutual understanding through training, guidance, and early communication is critical so that innovators know what is expected and regulators understand the technology's intent.

Issues & Implications:

Advanced technology solutions (like a robotics startup or a digital simulation provider) may come from industries with very different regulatory contexts (e.g. aerospace, IT, construction). When they step into nuclear decommissioning projects, they often underestimate the rigour and depth of documentation needed for regulatory approval. For instance, a vendor might develop a drone for radiological mapping with excellent technical performance, but be unaware of requirements such as approved calibration protocols, data traceability, or the need for the operator to have a specific license. Knowledge gaps manifest in incomplete safety cases or missing quality pedigree of components – which regulators will then reject or require rework. From the regulatory perspective, proposals involving novel technologies often include unfamiliar terminology or methods. When regulators lack sufficient familiarity with the underlying technology, it can hinder both effective oversight and clear communication with developers. The result can be frustration on both sides: developers feeling blindsided

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

by “unexpected” regulatory demands, and regulators receiving submissions that do not address fundamental safety criteria. Moreover, insufficient understanding may cause missed opportunities – a developer might overdesign or add unnecessary cost out of misunderstanding of what the regulator wants, or conversely, a regulator might impose extra conservatism if they are unsure the developer truly grasps the safety implications. All this slows down innovation and increases cost, and in worst cases can lead to regulatory rejection of a beneficial technology purely due to documentation or process issues rather than safety performance.

Existing Mechanisms:

Within the nuclear sector, there are mechanisms meant to bridge these gaps, though they are not always utilized by new entrants. Licensees (the facility operators) usually act as integrators, translating regulatory requirements down to their contractors and suppliers. They often impose nuclear-specific contract requirements (QA programs per ISO 19443 or NQA-1, safety culture expectations, etc.) on vendors. Additionally, many countries require that any entity providing nuclear-related equipment or services be under an established quality management system and sometimes an approval scheme (for example, France’s ASN requires certain contractors to be certified for nuclear work). These mechanisms ensure a baseline understanding, but smaller technology firms may not be familiar until they encounter them. There are also training programs and forums: the IAEA and national agencies run courses on nuclear regulatory basics (for instance, Argonne National Lab’s Decommissioning Training Course, or the NRC’s public licensing trainings). However, attendance is voluntary, and many technology developers may not be plugged into these networks. On the regulator side, most regulators have outreach offices or vendor design review programs where companies can seek clarification on requirements early. The UK ONR’s Innovation Liaison and the U.S. NRC’s Vendor Engagement programs are examples, as is the practice of pre-licensing vendor meetings. These are available but perhaps underutilized by new technology entrants who might not even know they should ask. In summary, the tools for knowledge transfer exist (standards, training, engagement opportunities), but the challenge is ensuring the right people take advantage of them at the right time.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

International Benchmarks & Practices:

A notable practice is early vendor engagement by regulators in the nuclear new build arena, which can be mirrored for waste management and decommissioning technology. For example, the Canadian Nuclear Safety Commission (CNSC) has a Vendor Design Review process primarily for reactor vendors, providing feedback on regulatory expectations even before a license application – this concept could be extended to robotics or digital tool developers in decommissioning. In the UK, ONR’s innovation hub and “innovation cafés” bring together regulators and industry in informal settings to discuss new technologies and their regulatory implications. These have been effective in demystifying regulatory expectations without the pressure of a formal submission. Another best practice is publishing plain-language guides for vendors. The U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) and NRC have issued guidance for non-nuclear companies partnering in nuclear work (e.g. DOE’s “due diligence for advanced nuclear technology companies” and Nuclear Innovation Alliance reports advising new companies on NRC processes [66]). Such documents break down the often-confusing regulatory structure into accessible terms. International forums like the NEA and IAEA also facilitate knowledge exchange – for example, the NEA’s workshops on supply chain oversight [67], highlight common pitfalls suppliers face and share lessons learned. A success story is the incorporation of non-nuclear technology companies in projects like Fukushima cleanup: Japanese authorities engaged robotics firms and through collaboration helped them meet nuclear safety requirements, resulting in successful deployments of specialized robots. This underscores that with guided collaboration, non-nuclear experts can adapt to nuclear rules.

Key Barriers and Root Causes:

The main challenge is a gap in communication and understanding. Nuclear regulation is often viewed as complicated and hard to access, filled with technical terms and background knowledge that people outside the field may not have. Technology developers may not even know what questions to ask. On the other side, regulators might assume certain prerequisites (like understanding of a “safety case” concept or the ALARA principle) that new vendors simply have not encountered. Another barrier is resource constraints: small enterprises may not have compliance departments to

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

study nuclear regulations in depth, and regulators may not have the mandate to educate each vendor individually. Additionally, mismatched expectations play a role: a technology innovator might be used to agile development and frequent iterations, whereas nuclear regulators expect a finalized, meticulously reviewed design before implementation – if this is not recognized early, conflict arises. Lastly, the nuclear sector has historically been insular, with a stable set of suppliers. Opening it up to high-technology newcomers means breaking down the siloed knowledge that long-time nuclear contractors take for granted. Without intentional effort, this knowledge is not transferred automatically.

Solutions and Recommendations:

The remedy lies in proactive education and open communication channels. Regulators and industry bodies should develop tailored training and guidance for advanced technology providers. This could include publishing a “Regulatory Primer for Nuclear Technology Innovators” – a concise guide that explains nuclear decommissioning regulatory processes, key safety and security requirements, and common documentation needs in plain language. Policymakers can support funding for workshops or incubator programs where technology startups in areas like AI, robotics, or BIM are paired with nuclear experts to learn about compliance early on. Embedding regulatory compliance as a topic in innovation competitions or funding calls (for example, requiring a regulatory feasibility section in proposals for decommissioning technology) can prompt developers to engage with the issue from day one.

Crucially, early engagement platforms must be promoted and expanded. Regulators should offer pre-submission consultation services specifically for novel technology integration – essentially an invitation: “Come talk to us before you design too far.” This could be formalized as a requirement that any decommissioning project planning to use unproven technology holds an early meeting with the regulator to agree on the approval approach. The ONR’s plan to use expert panels and “innovation cafés” is a good template, creating a safe, non-adversarial space for questions.

Licensees (decommissioning operators) also have a role: they should cascade knowledge to their supply chain. The recommendation is for operators to hold

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

onboarding sessions for vendors when contracting advanced technology work – explaining relevant regulatory constraints and even providing document templates or exemplars. This helps vendors align their deliverables (for example, a test report or risk assessment) with what regulators expect to see.

From the developer's side, investing in regulatory expertise is key. Hiring a consultant or advisor with nuclear regulatory experience to guide compliance can save time and cost later. Developers should treat the regulator as a stakeholder in design: incorporate regulatory requirements into the design criteria as one would include user requirements. For instance, if developing an AI system, assume you will need to explain its decision logic to regulators and design in logging and transparency features accordingly.

Finally, fostering a culture of open dialogue will go far. Regulators worldwide are increasingly open to engagement – initiatives like the IAEA Collaborating Centres can act as bridges, where technology experts and regulators jointly work on pilot projects, each learning the other's language. By demystifying regulations for innovators and demystifying innovations for regulators, the sector can ensure that compliance is a facilitator of safety and innovation, not a barrier. When all parties understand the “why” and “how” of regulatory requirements, compliance becomes more straightforward, and technologies can be deployed with confidence.

C-4 Technical Standards and Validation

Summary:

A major challenge for advanced technology in decommissioning is the lack of established technical standards and validation protocols tailored to these systems. There are few (if any) nuclear-industry standards governing the design, testing, and qualification of decommissioning robots or AI-driven systems. Likewise, validating such technologies in the harsh radioactive environment poses difficulties – conventional test criteria may not cover radiation tolerance, fail-safe behaviour, or reliability over long mission times. This absence of standards forces projects to improvise one-off validation approaches, creating uncertainty for both industry and regulators about whether a system is “proven” enough for nuclear use.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

Issues & Implications:

Unlike traditional nuclear equipment (pumps, pressure vessels, etc.) which have comprehensive codes and standards (ASME, IEC, etc.), advanced digital and robotic tools operate in a standards vacuum. For example, if an operator wants to deploy an autonomous robotic arm for waste sorting, there is no dedicated nuclear robotics standard defining requirements for radiation hardness, redundancy, or safety functions. In practice, this means regulators and licensees cannot simply point to a code for compliance; instead, they must perform extensive case-by-case assessments. This reinvents the wheel for each project and raises questions: How to demonstrate the robot will behave safely under all scenarios? What testing is sufficient to declare it reliable? The lack of standards also complicates third-party certification – typically, independent certification provides confidence (e.g. an ISO certification of a component). In robotics/AI for decommissioning, few accredited bodies exist to certify such systems, precisely because there is no agreed standard to certify against. According to industry experts, having safety standards that enable independent evaluation, and certification was a key factor in making industrial robots broadly acceptable; that infrastructure is currently missing for nuclear-specific applications [68].

Another aspect is validation in harsh environments. Many advanced systems must operate in high radiation, high contamination, or otherwise challenging conditions that are hard to fully emulate in testing. For AI algorithms (say for defect recognition or route planning), validating their accuracy and reliability is challenging even in normal settings – doing so under nuclear environmental stresses is harder. If a digital twin is used to support decommissioning decisions, validating its predictions against reality requires significant real-world data which may not exist until decommissioning is underway, a classic catch-22. The implication is that regulators may remain unconvinced about safety or efficacy, delaying approval. Furthermore, without standards, different countries or projects may adopt different ad hoc validation protocols, meaning results are not easily transferrable or comparable. One project's successful test might not persuade another country's regulator, leading to duplication of effort and cost. Overall, the absence of common standards creates a climate of uncertainty: innovators are

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

unsure how far to go in proving their technology, and regulators have little basis to accept results with confidence.

Existing Standards (or Lack Thereof):

Currently, implementers must lean on related industry standards as a proxy. For robotics, there are general standards such as ANSI/RIA R15.06 and ISO 10218 for industrial robot safety, or ISO 13482 for service robots, which define functional safety requirements (e-stops, collision avoidance, etc.). These are not nuclear-specific but do provide a baseline framework that can be partially applied. For software and AI, standards like IEEE 1012 (Verification and Validation) and ISO/IEC 61508 (functional safety of electrical/electronic systems) exist, and projects sometimes adapt these for robotics software. The European Space Agency's verification standard for autonomous systems is another reference that has influenced such standards. However, while these standards cover general reliability and safety, they “do not directly apply to the nuclear industry” without modification [68]. As noted in one study, adopting existing standards can help acceptance of a robotic system in nuclear, even if they weren't made for it, because they provide a structured evaluation and certification framework. Nuclear-specific standards are slowly emerging in adjacent areas: for example, IEC is working on standards for nuclear I&C that might extend to AI, and IAEA reports have begun to outline principles for autonomous systems in radiation environments. But as of now, a team deploying an AI or robotic solution must create a bespoke validation plan – often involving environmental testing (e.g. exposing components to radiation to measure degradation), functional testing (running the system through simulated tasks), and fail-safe demonstrations (showing it defaults to a safe state on malfunction). These plans must then be justified to regulators on their adequacy. In summary, de facto practice relies on borrowing non-nuclear standards plus project-specific test regimes, rather than following a unified nuclear standard.

International Benchmarks & Case Studies:

There have been notable efforts to define standards and shared practices. The OECD/NEA's Expert Group on robotic and remote systems highlights the need to “apply and adopt existing standards” in a way that assists evaluation of robots for

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

nuclear use. A good example is how NASA's use of the Robot Operating System (ROS) has informed nuclear robotics: NASA uses ROS in prototypes but not in mission-critical systems until verified, highlighting that open-source platforms need additional verification and validation (V&V). In the nuclear context, some projects have reached Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 6 (prototype demonstrated in relevant environment) but struggle to advance to TRL 8-9 (full deployment) due to lack of a formal qualification pathway. Additionally, UK's Nuclear AMRC (Advanced Manufacturing Research Centre) has been working on qualification of novel manufacturing and robotic techniques for nuclear, effectively developing internal guidelines that could evolve into standards. International harmonization bodies like ISO TC-85 (nuclear energy) have started sub-groups on digital instrumentation; for instance, ISO 19688 is a recent standard on computer security for nuclear I&C which, while not directly about AI, lays groundwork for digital system trustworthiness. A success story in standardization is the field of remote handling in fusion projects: ITER (the fusion reactor) developed extensive standards for remote maintenance robotics due to necessity. These standards (for reliability, maintainability, radiation tolerance) may be leveraged for decommissioning robotics as well. Essentially, where standards don't exist, leading organizations have created project-specific ones, which can serve as prototypes for formal standards.

Key Barriers and Root Causes:

The primary barrier is that standard development lags innovation – formal standards typically require broad consensus and years of data, which don't exist yet for these new technologies in nuclear applications. Without sufficient real-world deployments, standards bodies have limited evidence to inform their work, resulting in a bit of a stalemate. Another root cause is the diversity of technologies lumped together: “advanced technology” ranges from software algorithms to heavy robotics, each needing different standards (no one-size-fits-all), making the task daunting. Additionally, the nuclear context introduces extreme conditions (radiation, contamination) that most mainstream technology standards does not consider. Developing validation methods for these (e.g. how to certify an AI's decisions under radiation-induced upsets) is technically complex. The absence of test facilities and data

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

is also an issue: to create a standard for, say, radiation tolerance of drones, one needs data from consistent testing – but not many facilities can simulate nuclear environments for drones, and not many drones have been tested, so data is sparse. Economically, companies are reluctant to fund expensive qualification efforts without a clear return on investment (ROI), yet without those efforts, standards cannot progress. It's a classic market failure where each actor waits for the other. Finally, open-source software prevalent in robotics (like ROS) poses a validation challenge – it's constantly evolving and composed of modules of unknown pedigree. Traditional nuclear standards assume fixed designs and controlled change management, which is at odds with modern iterative development. This clash makes it harder to craft standards that regulators would accept for such software.

Solutions and Recommendations:

Accelerating the development of technical standards and validation frameworks is crucial. An immediate step is to leverage and augment existing standards: for each category (robotics hardware, control software, AI algorithms), identify the top relevant international standards and create nuclear annexes for them. For example, ISO 10218, which addresses robot safety, could be expanded with a “nuclear decommissioning” annex that addresses radiation tolerance, contamination controls (easy decontamination surfaces, etc.), and any emergency recovery requirements (how to retrieve a failed robot from a radiation area). Regulators and industry should collaborate in standard-development committees to ensure both practicality and safety. This could be done under the umbrella of IEC or ISO, or through IAEA technical documents that often precede formal standards.

In parallel, dedicated testbeds and certification processes for advanced technology could be established. Governments and research institutions can invest in facilities where robotics and digital systems can be tested against nuclear-relevant scenarios – for example, a mock-up facility with radiation sources to test robots' electronics and an operator control room to test remote operations and cybersecurity. Results from these testbeds can feed into confidence-building. Setting up a third-party certification scheme (perhaps via an organization like TÜV or DNV-GL who have nuclear and robotics expertise) would allow vendors to get an independent stamp that their product meets

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

certain criteria. As referenced in studies, having independent evaluation greatly aids adoption. Policymakers could incentivize this by subsidizing certification for SMEs developing qualifying decommissioning technology.

Guidance on V&V should be developed and shared. Regulators or standards bodies can publish recommended practices for V&V of AI and robotics. For example, a guideline might specify define the functional requirements of the system, identify failure modes, test the robot in a simulated decommissioning task X times without failure, perform radiation aging test to Y Gray total dose, etc., as a baseline. Formal verification and validation (V&V) play a critical role in ensuring system reliability by clearly specifying expected behaviours and verifying them across diverse scenarios. To operationalize this approach, especially in systems incorporating open-source software, guidelines can recommend strategies such as modular certification — certifying only critical modules or employing certified wrappers around uncertified components — to address the challenges of verifying heterogeneous and partially trusted code [69].

International collaboration is key: no single country likely has enough data or incentive alone. Therefore, an international working group on decommissioning technology qualification (possibly under NEA's CDLM committee or IAEA) should pool results from ongoing pilot projects and move toward consensus standards. For example, if France tests a decontamination robot and the UK tests a mapping drone, sharing both results can help define general requirements for remote systems. Regulators in this group could agree on a minimum validation set that each will accept, reducing duplication for vendors.

For technology developers, the recommendation is to design with validation in mind. They should familiarize themselves with any analogous standards (like automotive functional safety for AI – ISO 26262 – which could be relevant to autonomous vehicle-like robots) and voluntarily adhere to those processes (e.g. rigorous software V&V, documentation, safety analyses) even if not yet demanded, to build credibility. Developers should also engage early with potential certifiers or labs to test critical aspects (radiation tests, fail-safe tests), generating evidence that could later align with formal standards.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

In summary, establishing clear technical benchmarks and robust validation processes will provide confidence in advanced technologies. By doing the hard work now – crafting standards and running validation trials – the nuclear community can move from ad hoc acceptance to a standardized, streamlined approval of innovations. This will significantly reduce the current uncertainty and effort required to deploy advanced technology, while ensuring that safety and reliability are rigorously maintained in the face of nuclear decommissioning’s unique challenges.

C-5 International Harmonization and Certification

Summary:

Divergent national regulatory and certification schemes pose a challenge for deploying advanced technologies across different countries. What is accepted in one jurisdiction may face hurdles in another due to different requirements or processes. This lack of harmonization drives up costs (vendors must navigate multiple approval processes) and slows global diffusion of innovations. Aligning approaches – through mutual recognition, common standards, or joint certification – can reduce duplication and foster a larger market for decommissioning technologies, benefiting both innovation and safety by sharing best practices internationally.

Issues & Implications:

The nuclear regulatory landscape is country specific. Each nation’s regulator has its own set of rules, guidance, and licensing procedures, which evolved historically and legally. For traditional nuclear projects, this is already a challenge; for novel technologies it’s even more pronounced. A robotics system or AI tool proven in one country is not automatically approved elsewhere – the developer might have to undergo new rounds of testing or documentation to satisfy another regulator’s expectations. For example, a drone mapping system approved for radiation surveys in Country A might need to demonstrate compliance with different privacy or airspace rules in Country B, plus any nuclear security considerations unique to that country. Divergent certification extends to hardware classification: one country might classify a decommissioning robot as an industrial tool (with minimal nuclear regulatory involvement), while another may treat it as part of the nuclear facility, requiring a

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

license amendment or specific certification. Such inconsistencies create uncertainty for companies aiming to supply multiple decommissioning projects globally. They effectively shrink the market for a given innovation, because the effort to adapt and recertify for each country can be prohibitive. Variations in safety philosophy (probabilistic vs deterministic, for instance) may lead regulators to different conclusions about the acceptability of an AI decision-support tool, for instance. These differences can hamper multinational decommissioning programs or shared facilities. Stakeholders in HARPERS noted that different national regulations hinder broader markets for services and limit business growth. The inconsistency also means lessons learned are not easily transferable: if one country found a safe way to deploy an automated waste sorter, another country might not have a mechanism to recognize that experience and could impose entirely new requirements. From a safety perspective, this siloed approach can mean each country misses out on the collective improvement that comes from pooling data on technology performance and failures. Finally, international companies (and many decommissioning projects involve international contractors) face complexity in compliance management, which can lead to inadvertent non-compliance if a requirement in one jurisdiction is overlooked.

Existing Frameworks:

There are some efforts towards harmonization. At a high level, the IAEA safety standards provide a common language – virtually all regulators agree on fundamental principles (safety, security, environmental protection) which advanced technologies must support. Groups like WENRA (Western European Nuclear Regulators' Association) have issued reference levels for decommissioning safety, which indirectly harmonize expectations (e.g. all WENRA countries agree on the end-state criteria, etc.). However, these are generally high-level and do not drill down to technology-specific certification. In terms of certification, one existing tool is the CE marking and IEC standards for electrical/mechanical devices – a robotic system can carry internationally recognized marks (like CE, or IEC 61508 SIL ratings for safety functions). These are accepted across many countries for the industrial safety aspects of the system. But the nuclear-specific acceptability (e.g. nuclear safety function classification) is separate. The ISO 19443 quality management standard for nuclear

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

suppliers (essentially ISO 9001 with nuclear-specific requirements) is a harmonized approach to supplier quality; a vendor certified to ISO 19443 might be more readily accepted by multiple customers. Additionally, the concept of multinational design evaluation in reactors (MDEP) shows that regulators can collaborate on reviewing a design together. A parallel could be drawn for decommissioning technology: a few regulators could jointly assess a new technology pilot and agree on its use. On the industry side, some companies seek dual or multiple certifications proactively – for instance, obtaining both a European CE mark and a U.S. NRC equipment qualification. But without formal mutual recognition, this can only go so far.

International Benchmarks & Best Practices:

The drive for harmonisation in other nuclear areas offers lessons. For example, transport of radioactive material is an area with a high degree of international harmonization (IAEA's transport regulations are adopted by all countries), meaning a transport container certified in one country is accepted in another. A similar model could be pursued for certain decommissioning technology components or processes – e.g. an international certificate for a type of waste container or a type of radiation sensor. Another benchmark is the European CE marking process: once a product is CE-marked under relevant directives (machinery, EMC, etc.), it can be sold throughout the EU without country-by-country approval. If a parallel “nuclear CE” could be developed for decommissioning equipment (perhaps via an EU directive or an ENSREG initiative), it would greatly simplify cross-border technology deployment. The recent NEA report on robotic and remote systems aims to support broader adoption of RRS among NEA member countries, highlighting the value of harmonized approaches and shared protocols [70]. While formal joint certification frameworks for decommissioning technology do not yet exist, the report encourages collaborative mechanisms such as shared test protocols. One precedent is the CANDU Owners Group's work sharing RRS evaluation data across multiple Canadian sites. Similar to practices in aviation (e.g., FAA and EASA bilateral recognition), nuclear regulators such as the US NRC and Canada's CNSC have formal agreements to share technical evaluations. Though not yet routine in decommissioning, such collaborations could

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

enable regulators to jointly review and approve novel technologies—setting the groundwork for future mutual recognition.

Key Barriers and Root Causes:

National sovereignty and legal mandates mean regulators are ultimately responsible to their own country's laws and cannot automatically defer to another's approval. This is a fundamental reason for divergence – each regulator must follow their national regulatory framework, which may not allow simply “accepting” a foreign certification without their own review.. In addition, differing legacy contexts (e.g. one country's waste disposal approach might differ, affecting how they view a waste segregation technology) cause requirements to differ. Another barrier is that harmonization efforts require effort and compromise – it takes time for international groups to compare regulations and agree on alignment, and regulators are often stretched with domestic duties. Without strong incentive, the path of least resistance is to maintain the status quo. Commercial interests can play a role too: a country might impose unique requirements that favour its local suppliers or methodologies (unintentionally or not). Finally, even when technical standards align, the paperwork and process (licensing steps, documentation format) may differ enough to force duplication. All these factors are rooted in the historical independence of nuclear programs.

Solutions and Recommendations:

Moving towards greater international harmonization and mutual recognition is a multifaceted task. At the highest level, policymakers and regulators should actively participate in international initiatives like the IAEA's new Harmonization and Standardization Initiative [63], ensuring decommissioning and waste technologies are included in its scope. Regulators could establish bilateral or multilateral agreements to cooperate on decommissioning technologies approvals. For example, a cohort of regulators (perhaps in the EU or via the NEA) could agree that if one of them certifies a given tool or process, the others will accept or at least fast-track it. The model of the WENRA reference levels could be expanded: WENRA could develop reference levels for use of advanced technologies – e.g. a common approach to qualification of robotics

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

or use of digital twins in safety demonstration – which member regulators then implement nationally.

The creation of international certification bodies for nuclear decommissioning technology should be considered. An independent body under IAEA or an industry consortium could certify, for instance, a radiation-hardened robotic platform or an AI software for waste classification, against agreed criteria. If key regulators participate in setting those criteria, they are more likely to accept the certification's validity. Similar to how the IEC has certification schemes (IECEX for explosive atmospheres equipment, accepted globally), one could envision an "IEC NuclearDecom" scheme for equipment or software compliance.

Harmonizing standards represents a straightforward opportunity to ensure that emerging standards (as discussed in Cluster 4) are developed with international input and then adopted widely. The ISO and IEC framework already facilitates this – nuclear stakeholders should push for any new standards (for example, a standard for digital twin data integrity or for tele-operated robots in radiation areas) to be ISO/IEC standards, not just national. This way, a vendor following ISO XYZ can market globally.

Additionally, information-sharing platforms can help foster alignment among regulators. The NEA's working groups and IAEA's technical meetings on decommissioning should regularly include sessions on regulatory experience with new technology, so that regulators learn how others tackled an issue. Over time, this builds trust. The recent concept of "Regulatory sandboxes" on an international scale is promising – as noted, ONR's sandbox concept has sparked interest internationally [71]. By conducting sandbox exercises jointly (as NEA's RegLab will do for AI in multiple countries), regulators can converge on regulatory approaches together from the outset, rather than diverging.

For governments and the EU, providing a framework for cross-border use of decommissioning services will push harmonization. For example, if an EU country wants to use a robotic service from a company in another EU country, EU mechanisms could facilitate acceptance of the foreign regulator's oversight or at least minimize duplication (perhaps through the Nuclear Safety Directive framework). An EU-wide

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

regulatory sandbox for nuclear decommissioning technology could be funded, inviting companies to trial technology that multiple regulators observe.

On the industry side, vendors and operators can aid harmonization by standardizing their documentation and certification packages to meet the strictest common denominator. If a company anticipates needing approval in multiple countries, they should design to meet the highest standard among them and prepare one comprehensive package addressing all known regulatory points. Presenting this in international conferences and to various regulators can pre-empt questions and smooth acceptance. Industry associations (like WNA) can publish position papers recommending harmonized acceptance of certain well-understood technologies – for example, after enough successful uses of a technology, they could recommend that all regulators consider it proven.

In essence, recommendations are to: “review together, test together, and trust each other’s results.” By doing so, regulators will reduce redundant effort and focus resources on evaluating new innovations rather than re-evaluating the same innovation multiple times. This harmonization will expand the market for technology developers – incentivizing them to invest knowing an entire international market is accessible – while simultaneously upholding high safety standards through the global pooling of expertise and data.

C-6 *Regulator Expertise and Security Concerns*

Summary:

The rapid development of advanced technologies has exposed gaps in the regulatory technical know-how, as well as introduced new cybersecurity and safety-security interface concerns that existing classification schemes do not adequately address. Regulators may not yet have sufficient in-house knowledge of AI algorithms, software validation, or robotics engineering to confidently evaluate these systems. Additionally, digital and connected technologies blur the lines between nuclear safety systems and IT systems, raising questions about how to classify and protect them (for example, are they part of the critical safety envelope or not?). Uncertainty in cybersecurity

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

categorization and a lack of specialized technology expertise can lead to overly cautious or inconsistent regulatory responses.

Issues & Implications:

If regulators do not fully understand a new technology, there is a risk of either over-regulation or underestimation. Over-regulation could manifest as requiring unnecessarily stringent measures (perhaps treating a simple surveying AI as if it were a reactor protection system software) out of an abundance of caution, which could stifle innovation. Underestimation is the opposite – missing a potential failure mode or security vulnerability because the technology’s intricacies were not appreciated. Both are dangerous: the former from an innovation standpoint, the latter from safety/security. Specifically, many advanced tools involve software and networking – areas where cybersecurity is a major concern. Nuclear regulations typically categorize systems by their safety function (safety-class, safety-related, non-safety, etc.) and have separate categories for security systems. But an AI-driven decommissioning tool does not fit neatly: it might not be safety-critical, yet a cyber compromise of it (say hacking a waste-sorting robot) could cause operational chaos or even radiological hazards. Regulators are grappling with how to classify such systems for cybersecurity:

- Do they fall under nuclear security regulations?
- Are they part of the “critical digital assets” list or just industrial IT?

Ambiguity here can lead to inconsistent requirements – one inspector might demand full defence-in-depth cyber protections, while another might treat it as auxiliary. The ONR, for example, identified the need to establish clear standards and arrangements for categorization and classification of cyber systems going forward [62]. Until clarified, licensees might default to highest-level protections (which are costly and complex to implement) or risk leaving vulnerabilities unaddressed if they guess incorrectly. Another aspect is the safety-security interface: advanced technology like drones or remote systems could introduce security issues (e.g. unauthorized access or data leakage) that overlap with safety. Regulators must ensure neither aspect is overlooked – a task requiring expertise in both nuclear safety analysis and cybersecurity.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

Additionally, internal capacity is an issue. Regulators have highlighted risks of insufficient capability and capacity in their strategic risk registers. If a regulator lacks an AI specialist, for instance, they must rely on external support or err on the side of caution. This can slow down reviews and make interactions less effective. It also puts pressure on the few specialists available, potentially causing bottlenecks. Finally, the workforce issue is long-term – regulators need to train or hire new skill sets, which can lag behind immediate project needs.

Existing Situation:

Recognizing these gaps, some regulators are actively building expertise. The UK's ONR developed an AI Strategy and hired data scientists to understand AI implications [72]. They completed an AI regulatory sandbox pilot with technical experts, improving staff understanding of AI systems' behaviour and failure modes. The NRC has an Office of Nuclear Regulatory Research that has been studying digital I&C and cybersecurity for years, issuing guidelines on secure development and reviewing AI use cases [73]. The IAEA provides some support via its nuclear security series documents (e.g. computer security guidelines for nuclear facilities) which member states adapt. However, these efforts are in early stages relative to the challenge. On cybersecurity classification: regulators like ONR and the U.S. NRC do require licensees to identify critical digital assets and protect them, but these frameworks were developed mainly for reactor control systems and physical protection systems, not for miscellaneous digital tools. ONR's current strategy includes improving cyber security categorization and potentially expanding its regulatory scope in cyber domain by 2025. Some progress has been made in clarifying that any digital system connected to plant operations must undergo cyber risk assessment. But formal classification (e.g. does a decommissioning site's digital twin count as a Category I security asset?) can still be a grey zone that each licensee interprets. In terms of regulator expertise, agencies often collaborate, e.g., regulators might consult technical support organizations (like ASNR in France, or national labs in the US) for specialist analysis of a novel technology. This supplements in-house knowledge but is not a substitute for building internal competency. Developing internal technical strength is important to ensure that

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

regulatory bodies remain self-reliant, credible, and capable of addressing evolving challenges independently.

International Benchmarks:

International cooperation can help fill expertise gaps. For example, the NEA has organized regulators-only workshops on digital innovation to share knowledge. The CANUKUS collaboration (Canada-UK-US) on AI regulation, suggests leading regulators teaming up to share strategies and training (the sandbox results in the UK were shared with counterparts abroad;[74]). IAEA's nuclear security recommendations are also evolving – recently, more attention is given to cyber-physical systems. A good benchmark outside nuclear is how aviation authorities handle new technology: they often have specialized units for new aircraft technology and cybersecurity, and they exchange personnel internationally. Nuclear regulators have started doing similar secondments and training exchanges.

A notable success in expertise development is the historical example of the Halden Human Technology Organisation (HTO) Project, where technology developers, regulators, industry and researchers from 12 countries and 48 approved third parties collaborate to study human-machine interfaces and reactor software, creating a shared knowledge base that benefited regulatory bodies internationally. A modern equivalent could be joint research centres for decommissioning technology evaluation. On the cybersecurity front, standards like IEC 62645 (computer security for nuclear instrumentation) provide a common baseline; regulators globally have begun to endorse such standards, implicitly classifying systems that fall under those standards. The NEA's cybersecurity benchmarking exercises and the EU's civil nuclear cyber strategy are aligning practices, which will help clarify expectations for advanced technology (e.g. if a robot is on the plant network, it must meet certain cyber controls uniformly).

Key Barriers and Root Causes:

These issues stem from the fact that advanced technology introduces skills that traditional nuclear regulatory staff were not initially hired or trained for. Recruiting and retaining data scientists or robotics engineers within nuclear regulators can be

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

challenging given competition from industry and other sectors. Budget constraints and the relatively small number of needed experts mean regulators might not have full-time specialists in each emerging area. Another cause is that cybersecurity is a moving target – threats evolve quickly, and regulations in nuclear security historically focus on physical protection and control systems, not general IT. Thus, applying old security classification schemes (designed for say, physical access or sabotage scenarios) to digital scenarios is non-trivial. Ambiguity arises because the consequences of cyber incidents on new technology are not well quantified: does hacking a decommissioning robot present a nuclear risk or just an operational nuisance? Different views on that cause classification debates. Additionally, siloing between safety and security within organizations can lead to gaps – a new technology might fall between safety oversight (who think it's not safety-critical) and security oversight (who focus on traditional access control systems), resulting in a blind spot unless clearly assigned. The inherent conservatism of nuclear regulation means if in doubt, a regulator might impose very strict measures; but lacking expertise, they may not even know the right strict measures to impose, hence defaulting to simply disallowing or delaying until they understand better.

Solutions and Recommendations:

Strengthening regulator understanding and know-how is probably the most important aspect here. Regulatory bodies and governments should allocate resources for hiring or training personnel in AI, robotics, software engineering, and cybersecurity. This might include exchange programs with technology companies or national labs, so regulators get hands-on familiarity. Cross-disciplinary teams should review advanced technology proposals – e.g. a nuclear safety specialist paired with a cyber specialist – to ensure all angles are covered. Regulators might consider establishing an internal “Advanced Technology Unit” whose job is to stay on top of technology trends, advise licensing divisions, and develop internal guidelines. The output of ONR’s pilot sandbox on AI, for instance, should be distilled into training for all inspectors and into internal regulatory guidance on AI.

On the cybersecurity classification question, regulators and operators need to develop a clear categorization schema for digital assets in decommissioning. One

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

recommendation is to update nuclear facility security plans to explicitly list new technology systems and assign them a security category based on potential consequence of compromise. If a digital twin is only for simulation, perhaps classify it as low security importance; if a robotic system could potentially disperse contamination if hacked, classify it higher. Regulators should issue guidance on how to make that determination. ONR's plan to "establish... arrangements for categorisation and classification of cyber security systems" by 2025 [62], is a model approach – all regulators should do similarly, and ideally coordinate so these classifications are comparable internationally. The guidance might mirror safety classification but for security (e.g. Category 1: could cause significant radiological release if compromised, Category 2: lesser impact, etc., with examples of systems in each).

Collaboration with cybersecurity agencies is also advised – nuclear regulators can work with national cyber authorities to ensure they are leveraging the latest threat intelligence and protective techniques for these new IT-based systems. For instance, drawing on expertise from government CERT teams or implementing frameworks like the NIST Cybersecurity Framework tailored too nuclear.

To address expertise gaps in the interim, use of external Technical Support Organizations (TSOs) should be streamlined. Regulators could have standing contracts or MOUs with institutes that have the needed expertise (for example, a robotics research centre) to consult on regulatory reviews. While not a long-term substitute, it ensures no technology goes un-scrutinized due to lack of in-house skills.

Innovation sandboxes and pilot projects should explicitly include regulator staff participation, as those are hands-on learning opportunities. This was done in the ONR AI sandbox – regulator staff worked alongside industry on an AI use case, significantly boosting their understanding. Expanding this concept to other technology (e.g. have inspectors participate in controlling a robot or using a digital twin themselves in a demo) will build intuition that no amount of reports can provide.

On the industry side, transparency and support to regulators can help. Developers should be prepared to explain their technology from basics, provide training sessions to the regulator on how it works, and share source information (maybe even source

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

code under confidentiality) to allow deep dives. They should also incorporate robust cybersecurity measures by design and present a clear cyber risk assessment to regulators; to show they have considered those issues – this will assist regulators in making classification decisions.

Finally, updating regulatory guidance to incorporate new technology considerations will formalize the knowledge. For instance, decommissioning regulatory guides could be revised to include a section on use of remote/robotic tools and expectations for their management, or a nuclear security guide could include “mobile and digital systems” as a category with prescribed controls. The act of writing these updates often forces clarification of classification and roles.

In conclusion, strengthening regulator expertise and clarifying cyber/safety classifications are essential to safely integrating advanced technologies. Regulators who understand the technology can apply requirements intelligently and proportionately, and clear categorization of new digital systems will ensure that neither security nor safety is compromised. The goal is a regulator that is as modern as the industry it oversees – equipped to evaluate AI and robotics with the same confidence it evaluates a pump or a valve – and rules that squarely address the new risks these technologies bring. By pursuing training, collaboration, and guideline updates now, we future-proof regulation for the ongoing digital transformation of nuclear decommissioning.

C-7 Regulatory issues identified in WP5

The previous sections outlined the main challenges related to the use of advanced technologies in nuclear decommissioning. As part of this, four issues were identified as being specifically regulatory in nature. The table below provides a summary of these issues, including the reasons they are considered regulatory, the implications they present, and suggested ways to address them.

Regulatory framework and criteria report (WP6)

Table 9: This table presents a condensed overview of the four issues identified as regulatory in nature, as discussed in the preceding analysis. It outlines the rationale for their classification, the practical implications for nuclear decommissioning projects, and suggested solutions aimed at addressing the specific regulatory gaps.

Regulatory Issue	Rationale (Why it is Regulatory)	Implications	Suggested Solutions / Recommendations
Lack of standardised regulations for digital twin implementation in nuclear decommissioning	Digital twins are increasingly used to support planning and safety decisions, yet no specific regulatory guidance exists, creating ambiguity about their role and compliance requirements.	Projects face delays or inconsistent reviews due to lack of clear requirements; safety cases using digital twins may be challenged or require case-by-case approval.	Develop guidance documents or regulatory notes defining acceptable uses, validation approaches, and safety case integration for digital twins.
Lack of established regulatory framework for AI applications in nuclear industry	AI technologies are being introduced into safety and operational processes, but without a clear framework, there's uncertainty about validation, oversight, and accountability.	Unclear pathways for AI integration delay adoption; developers may overcompensate with unnecessary controls or face rework if regulatory expectations shift.	Create an AI regulatory framework, possibly through sandbox trials, to establish approval pathways, performance criteria, and documentation standards.
Regulatory development pace significantly lags behind technological advancements	Most regulatory processes were built around traditional technologies and have not evolved to match the speed of innovation, creating a gap in timely regulatory support.	Technological solutions may be ready before a regulatory response exists, resulting in underutilisation or missed opportunities for safer, more efficient processes.	Introduce agile regulatory processes that allow for interim positions, pilot evaluations, and regular review cycles to adapt to emerging technologies.
Unclear classification of cybersecurity as a regulatory or technical issue	Cybersecurity risks touch both operational safety and IT infrastructure, but current frameworks don't clearly assign responsibility, leading to inconsistencies in protection measures.	Varying interpretations by different authorities can result in over- or under-regulation, potentially exposing systems to risk or imposing unnecessary burdens.	Clarify cybersecurity classification criteria and responsibilities in updated guidance, distinguishing between IT threats and nuclear safety concerns.